

THE ACCOUNTS OF NOVICE TEACHERS IN AN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL EXPLORATION

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 30

Issue 10

Pages: 1509-1537

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2928

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14662881

Manuscript Accepted: 12-27-2024

The Accounts of Novice Teachers in an Inclusive Education: A Phenomenological Exploration

Lady Anne A. Dayanan,* Rhea Joy B. Semblante
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This main objective of this qualitative study was to gain a comprehensive understanding of the lived experiences of novice teacher teaching students with special needs. Using purposive sampling and inclusion criteria, the participating 14 novice teacher from public schools in Davao region were identified. All of them participated in the in-depth interview. Results revealed the lived experiences of the participants: Dealing with challenges in interaction with students with special needs, implementing teaching strategies to meet the needs of students, effectiveness in adapting teaching, and using diverse instructional materials. In response to the challenges they have encountered, they deemed the following novice teachers cope with the challenges in teaching students with special need. The following themes were: individualized support and differentiation, building rapport and relationships, collaboration and professional development, flexibility and adaptability and strong motivation from one's students. Upon reflecting on their entire experience, they arrived at the following insights: The value of perseverance and resilience, establishing positive relationship with students with special needs, empathy and compassion, continuous learning and collaboration and importance of strong parents' support. The results of this study were deemed significant by the participants, teachers, students and researchers.

Keywords: *experiences, novice teachers, thematic analysis, qualitative research, phenomenological exploration*

Introduction

Students with inclusive education have long been a significant concern in general education in mainstreaming classroom settings, where some learners can be integrated in the mainstream education. These students have the right to access all learning resources and participate in group activities within a typical classroom environment. Studies show novice teachers express a desire to include students with special educational needs in their classrooms setting. However, they often lack the necessary knowledge and skills to effectively address the educational demands of these students. This highlights the need for better novice teacher training and teaching strategies and access to information on creating inclusive and effective learning environments (Subarna et al., 2022).

In the America, novice teachers in special education are an ongoing problem in school districts throughout the United States face the dilemma of special education teachers. These teachers leave the Profession within two years of employment because they do not have the necessary support or preparation to meet the needs of their students with disabilities and many other professional challenges that confront them daily. The development and implementation of mentoring programs are essential for novice teachers in special education. These teachers require continuous support to develop confidence and professional proficiency in teaching students with disabilities the mentoring relationship can help novice teachers in special education to improve and develop the necessary skills and confidence to positively impact student achievement. Various mentoring programs have been developed and implemented to provide services to novice teachers in general education. However, research was lacking regarding specific areas of concern for novice teachers' special education. Therefore, this study was necessary and timely to shed light on this issue and provide information for necessary changes and improvements in support of special education teachers (Geiger et al., 2018).

In Cebu City, Philippines, the inclusive education has been working on implementing various programs and initiatives to support inclusive education. One such initiative is the "Inclusive Education for All" program, which provides training and support to teachers, parents, and school administrators on how to best meet the needs of all students. To train novice teachers to include students with disabilities in their classrooms. This training covers topics such as adapting instruction for students with disabilities, creating a supportive learning environment, and working collaboratively with parents. Also been working to develop policies that support inclusive education. One such policy is the creation of Special Education (SPED) schools, which are designed specifically for students with special needs. These schools provide services and accommodations, such as smaller class sizes, specialized instruction, and adaptive technology, which help ensure that these students can thrive in an academic setting (Alber et al., 2019).

The researcher conducted a study because there was an urgency to conduct this study as it to address a significant gap in the field of inclusive education. Specifically, the study seeks to explore the experiences of novice teachers as they implement inclusive practices in their classrooms. This is an important area of research because novice teachers are often the first to implement new initiatives, such as inclusive education. As a result, the experiences of novice teachers can provide valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities of implementing inclusive education. By understanding the experiences of novice teachers, we can better support them as they implement inclusive practices. Overall, the research title The Accounts of Novice Teachers in an Inclusive Education: A Phenomenological Exploration is timely and significant. Despite the challenges, novice teachers can be successful in implementing inclusive practices. The study provides recommendations for supporting novice teachers as they implement inclusive practices.

The study has social relevance because there is to provide a better understanding of the experiences of novice teachers who have

implemented inclusive education in their classrooms. This understanding can be used to develop and evaluate interventions that can support novice teachers in implementing inclusive education. Additionally, this understanding can be used to inform the development of policies and practices that promote inclusive education in schools. The study has the potential to make a positive impact on society by helping to improve the quality of education for all students. By supporting novice teachers in implementing inclusive education, we can help to ensure that all students have the opportunity to learn and thrive.

In connection, there are several international studies conducted in relation to novice teachers teaching inclusive education such as students with special needs, including the studies of Subarna et al., (2022), titled “Teaching Students with Inclusive education in Regular Classes,” Hazmi et al., (2018), titled “Universal Design for Learning to Support Access to the General Education Curriculum for Students with special needs” and Chiwandire et al., (2019) “Funding And Inclusion In Higher Education Institutions For Students With Special Needs”. They gave us useful ideas on how to teach students with special needs better. These studies collectively provide valuable insights into novice teacher effective teaching approaches for individuals with special needs. This holistic approach contributes significantly to the field of special education needs, enhancing our understanding of how to support and educate to students with special needs.

With these, the study wants to provide a deeper understanding of the experiences of novice teachers as they navigate the challenges and rewards of implementing inclusive education practices in their classrooms. Through a phenomenological exploration, the study aims to uncover the lived experiences of these teachers, capturing their unique perspectives and insights on inclusive education. The use of the term accounts in the title highlights the importance of the teachers' own voices and perspectives. The study seeks to amplify their voices and give them a platform to share their stories and experiences. The inclusion of the phrase A Phenomenological Exploration underscores the qualitative nature of the study, emphasizing the focus on understanding the lived experiences of the participants. Overall, the research title effectively conveys the purpose of the study, which is to delve into the experiences of novice teachers in inclusive education through a phenomenological approach. The title is concise, clear, and informative, and it accurately reflects the focus and objectives of the research.

The copies of the study were disseminated to various research conferences and concerned agencies to facilitate scholarly exchange and utilization of research-based discovery.

Research Questions

The aim of this study is to determine the Accounts of Novice in on Inclusive Education: A Phenomenological Exploration. Specifically, this attempts to achieve the following objectives:

1. What are the lived experiences encountered by novice teachers teaching students with special needs?
2. How do novice teachers cope with the challenges in teaching students with special needs?
3. What insights do novice teachers can share with regards to teaching students with special needs?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized qualitative research on a phenomenological approach. According to Bhandari (2023), qualitative research design is a collection and analyzation of non-numerical data for comprehensive understanding of thoughts, ideas and experiences of the participants. Through this design, researcher can gather in-depth insights that delves into the phenomena or produced new ideas for the study which taken from the participants that are involved in the said event.

In order to further understand the challenges, coping mechanism from those challenges and insights from the particular phenomenon they have experienced, this study employs qualitative type of research applying the approach of phenomenology. Qualitative research is a type of research where it does not require numerical data but more of the syntactic, semantic and pragmatic data to arrive at an exploratory means of in-depth collection, analysis and discussion of data through the means of interviewing (Creswell, 1998).

This study utilized a qualitative research design on phenomenological approach which aimed to have a finer understanding of the in-depth analysis of the experiences, the coping strategies and the insights of our informants. It used an inquiry developed from in-depth data analysis. The information was acquired through interviews, observations, discussions and representations. The data was then read and reread and culled for like phrases and themes that are then grouped to form clusters of meaning. I generated the description of each case as well as the theme of the case I was studied.

This phenomenological research is a design of inquiry developed from philosophy and psychology in which I can described teaching the inclusive education in the classroom setting or the mainstreaming in teaching students with special needs of novice teacher in Davao Del Norte. It focuses on the challenges on how they manage they're during their teaching in the inclusive education and which also involves on their feelings, views, motivational factors, challenges and perceived effects of the said experiences in their teaching profession.

Moreover, this would also be the most appropriate research methodology because the concern of the study is to know how people make

sense of their lived experiences in teaching with special needs. The researcher wants to know what the participants thought about their teaching experiences in the inclusive education in the classroom setting. The researcher focuses on the participants' expectations, causes, motives, objectives, and values about the experiences they encountered in their teaching. The researcher will also try her best to capture the participants' perspectives as accurately as possible. It is emphasized that through phenomenology, special events that happened as participants included their experiences could be understood better through lengthy discussions. The researcher is interested to know how things happen as experienced by the novice teachers in teaching the inclusive education in the classroom setting and how they interpret these experiences and find meaning in these experiences.

In the context, I used phenomenological approach to explore the lived experiences of novice teachers in inclusive education. Phenomenology is a qualitative research approach that seeks to understand the meaning of experiences from the perspective of those who have had them. This approach is well-suited for this study because it will allow the researchers to gain a deep and nuanced understanding of the challenges and rewards that novice teachers face as they implement inclusive practices in their classrooms. The qualitative approach that utilizes a phenomenological framework to explore the lived experiences of novice teachers in inclusive education settings. This design is well-suited for gaining a deeper understanding of the participants' perspectives and uncovering the underlying meanings and themes inherent in their experiences.

Participants

The key participants of this study are the novice teacher who teaching students with special needs in all public elementary schools in Davo Del Norte. Fourteen (14) participants are will undergo in-depth interviews (IDI), wherein each of them was interviewed individually by me. wherein all of them gathered in one question that I had presented to them. This determined number was in adherence to the suggestion of Creswell (2013) that the ideal number of participants in a qualitative study range from 4 to 15 participants. By having this set of participants in a qualitative research study, high data saturation was achieved in the data collection process.

In selecting the respondents for this study, purposive sampling will be use to ensure that those who will give the necessary data for this study is eligible. The method is a non-probability type of sampling which guarantee to gather appropriate and useful information about the phenomenon being studied. In that case, the study will be rich and descriptively deep in analyzing process. Purposive sampling method use to examine the similarities and differences of sample size to look for homogeneity in the data gathered (Smith et al., 2009).

This study will utilize a qualitative research design on phenomenological approach which aims to have a finer understanding of the in-depth analysis of the experiences, the coping strategies and the insights of our informants. It uses an inquiry develop from in-depth data analysis. The information was acquired through interviews, observations, discussions and representations. The data was then read and reread and culled for like phrases and themes that are then grouped to form clusters of meaning. I generate the description of each case as well as the theme of the case I was study.

This phenomenological research is a design of inquiry develop from philosophy and psychology in which I can described inclusive education of novice teacher teaching students with special needs in Davao del Norte. It focuses on the challenges on how they manage they're during their transportation and which also involves on their feelings, views, motivational factors, challenges and perceive effects of the said experiences in their teaching profession.

In recruitment process, there are criteria that need to be followed. First, each participant must be elementary teacher and officially employed in public elementary school of Davao Del Norte. Second, must have 6 months to 1 year in service teaching experience in teaching inclusive education Lastly, the participant must use study approaches.

Procedure

In this study, as the researcher, anticipate steps to incorporate in gathering data. Firstly, I will seek permission in the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS), Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) and Schools Principals within Davao Del Norte to verify the cooperation of the institution that will greatly help me to find and recruit participants for my study. In addition, as a researcher i will also ensure that each of the participant is well aware of the study before in agreeing to be part of my research study. Secondly, identifying and recruiting participants using the purposive sampling method to ensure that they are suitable and can give appropriate and useful information that will be utilized in the proceeding chapters.

In order to have integrity upon conducting and in the recruitment process, I will process consent in agreement forms before undergoing the interview session, which day are able to read the term and condition before signing and participating that involves statement that their participation is an act of voluntary and its part of the success of the research.

During interview session, the researcher will be domain instrument for the collection of data i will utilize tools like smartphone for recording process to ensure the proper transcribing of data's before translating to standard English language. Participant will also choose the time, location, and the date to be held the actual interview. Also, during the interview, i am going to prohibit myself to interfere while they are sharing their experiences, not unless, they ask clarification about the question and have difficulties on it for me to refine and able to make the question easy for them to understand.

Finally, after interview session, transcribing will be the next step and retrieve emerging themes using thematic analysis approaches.

The extracted themes will be given to the data analyst which knowledge is a line for the concept language research for verification and approval.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was one of the most intricate and less extensively discussed phases in the qualitative project (Thorne, 2000). In this study, the researcher employed thematic analysis to scrutinize the data collected. Thematic analysis, as a systematic process, was integrated into the data analysis, enabling the connection of thematic frequencies with the overall content, which proved highly advantageous. This approach facilitated the identification of variables and elements that shaped the phenomenon observed by the participants, given that their interpretations offered valuable justifications for their behaviors, attitudes, and ideas. The analysis encompassed data reduction, data visualization, and data conclusions, all essential steps within thematic analysis that assisted in inferring and validating the gathered data (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

The process of writing up field notes and transcriptions involved the selection, focus, simplification, abstraction, and transformation of emerging data, commonly referred to as data reduction. This approach enabled the researcher to effectively organize and condensed the extensive dataset, making it more manageable. Additionally, during data reduction, decisions were made regarding which aspects of the acquired data should be emphasized, minimized, or omitted entirely to shed light on the pertinent issues. To facilitate the integration, management, sorting, and categorization of the substantial qualitative data employed in this methodology, the researcher enlisted the support of a data analyst specialist (Creswell, 2013).

Ethical Considerations

In this study, the primary focus was on teachers in the field of education, with a secondary emphasis on educators in general. Ensuring the safety and security of these participants was of utmost importance to maintain their trust and confidence in the research process. The researcher upheld ethical principles, including respect for persons, beneficence, justice, consent, and confidentiality (Boyatzis, 1998; Mack et al. 2005).

These principles guided the researcher in conducting the study with integrity, respecting the rights and well-being of the participants, and maintaining the confidentiality of their information. By adhering to these ethical principles, the researcher aimed to create a safe and trustworthy environment for the participants, fostering a positive research experience and contributing to the overall validity and reliability of the study.

To ensure that research is conducted systematically and ethically, it is essential to highlight and adhere to ethical codes and regulations concerning the participants. This qualitative study focused on the fundamental principles of ethical research, such as obtaining informed consent, maintaining confidentiality and anonymity, avoiding harm, promoting reciprocity, and reflecting on issues of power, empowerment, and ownership (Shenton, 2004).

Respect for persons pertains to the courtesy of the researcher towards the participants as well as their rights to autonomously decide in taking part in the study. This means that the research becomes ethical when the researcher provides the prospect participants adequate information and understanding about the research study, and the provision of this information leads to the participants' informed consent to voluntarily take part in the study (Munhall, 2015; Scott, 2013). It is the researcher's obligation to exploit the weaknesses of the research participants. Self sufficiency will avoid maintaining trust, friendship, and confidence among participants and the researcher. Before the administration of interviews, I asked permission from the researcher. Before the administration of interviews, I asked permission from the parents and the participants themselves and I adjusted upon their availability. Therefore, I set the interview schedule ahead of time. This was done to ensure that I was not a reason that our participants may have to be absent from their respective classes; also, to avoid delay or cancellation of their important errands.

Beneficence requires a commitment to minimizing the risks of the participants rather than maximizing profits that are due to them. The anonymity of the interviewee was kept in order not to put each participant at risk at all times, participants were protected, so overfilled information was not left unattended or unprotected (Bricki & Green, 2007).

Consent is another most important way of showing respect to persons during research. This is to let all participants became aware of the purpose and objectives of the research study that they are going to involve. Written consent was provided for them to get their approval. After getting their positive response, they actively participated in the in-depth interview and focus group discussion.

In order to respect my participants, I concern to ask them if they have a sincere interest in taking part in this study. They were additionally encouraged to participate of their own free will. An informed consent form that my participants signed to indicate their voluntary involvement serves as proof of this. In order to inform the participants about the purpose of the study and to provide them with the information they need to decide whether or not to join, this form also stipulated preliminary information on the study's methodology, design, and procedures. Participants who decided not to participate in the study were allowed to leave, with the assurance that their data will remain confidential even after the conduct of the study.

Confidentiality towards the results and findings including the safety of all the data and the participants, coding system, and pseudonyms will be used to hide the identity of the participants. As suggested, all materials including the videotapes, encoded transcripts, notes, and

other materials that secure important information from the participants destroyed after the data are analyzed (Maree & Westhuizen, 2007). I ensured that each participant was identified using discrete coding when I transcribed all of their responses. The Republic Act 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which was the foundation for this measure, states that any information that might potentially be used to identify participants, such as their name, gender, ethnicity, or employment or location information, should be carefully worded to avoid violating the confidentiality of the participants. Therefore, in order to address this, appropriate coding and other methods were implemented and followed in order to secure the participants' identity. Additionally, none of the necessary documents for this study that my research participants had to fill out ever required them to provide their names. The researcher also conducted an in-person transcription of the interviews.

Justice requires reasonable allocation of the risks benefits as the results of the study. Therefore, acknowledging the contribution of all the respondents should be highlighted as they become an integral part of the success of this study. They must be given due credits in all their endeavors (Bloom & Crabtree, 2006).

To address justice in my study, I made sure that fairness was given to the research participants without bias. I had presented the research participants with subjected risk and benefits. I made sure that the participants were picked fairly based on the roght procedure for participants selection, which involved the use of the purposive sampling approach. As a result, no eligible volunteers had their study participation disallowed on the basis of their personal classification (age, gender, sex, ethnicity, etc.).

Throughout the IDI sessions, it a point to keep the interviewees at ease and secured during the entire discussion, I gave valuable gifts to all my participants as payment for the time and effort they put into helping me complete this study.

Results and Discussion

Participants

The participants of the study were the elementary novice teachers who teaching students with special needs from the public schools in Davao del Norte. They were all novice teachers who were teaching for almost months to two years. There were total of ten (14) novice teacher involved in the study: five (5) males and nine (9) females. As shown in Table 1, a total of 14 individuals took part in this study, comprising 14 participants for the in-depth interview. Among these 14 participants, six newly hired teachers were from School A and eight newly hired teachers were assigned in School B.

In-depth Interview. There were 14 key participants in this study. They were all elementary novice teachers coming from a different school in Davao del Norte. According to Heaton (2021) methodology, each informant for the in-depth interviews was given a pseudonym during the interview sessions. The researcher asked the participants if they wanted to be interviewed. The researcher got what she wanted, and both the interviewer and the interviewee were pleased with the result, resulting in a seamless flow and open communication whenever extra or probing questions were required. The participants were given the choice to refuse to respond to any question they considered unbeneficial or in opposition to their wishes. To ensure confidentiality, the information or data collected during the interviews was treated with the utmost confidentiality. Only the researcher and the participants had access to this information, which was shared verbally but not included in the study due to its nature.

Table 1. *Participants of the Study*

<i>In-Depth Interview (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Code</i>
Art	Female	IDI-01
Mr. Smile	Male	IDI-02
Chinita	Female	IDI-03
Sunflower	Female	IDI-04
Ms. Curly	Female	IDI-05
Mayumi	Female	IDI-06
Mysterious	Male	IDI-07
Harmony	Female	IDI-08
King bee	Male	IDI-09
Baby Ma'am	Female	IDI-10
Mr. Friendly	Male	IDI-11
Whip smart	Female	IDI-12
Music	Male	IDI-13
Chatterbox	Female	IDI-14

In order to adhere to the data collection process, the researcher used smartphones to record the participants' responses during the interview. Additionally, the researcher requested permission from all the participants to record the entire conversation during the interview, and they all politely agreed. All participants were accommodating and comprehended the request, except for one condition: that their identities remain anonymous in the study.

All participants in each case were given pseudonym in order to protect the identities of all the participants. The pseudonyms were chosen by the participants themselves, based on their preference and distinctive physical characteristics, as well as their responses and

attitudes observed throughout the interview sessions. Pseudonyms were also given to each participant to protect their identities as well. For instance, Arts was the name given to the participant who does painting before the interview session, while Mr. Smile was the name given to the participant who was always smiling during the interview. Chinita was the name given to the participant who had really cute eyes, while Sunflower was given to the participant who was as pretty as sunflower. Ms. Curly was the name given to the participant with curly hair. Mayumi was given to the participant who had aura of being demure and humble. Mysterious was the name given to the informant really looks like a mysterious one. Harmony was the nickname given to the participant because he was balanced and harmonious, promoting unity and understanding. King bee was the name given to the participant who treated himself as a king. Baby Ma'am was given to the youngest among all the participants while Mr. Friendly was given to the participant who has the personality of being friendly. Whip smart is to was the name given to the participant her because during the interview, her wit is swift and clever, in every question she showcased her intelligence and ability to deliver witty remarks effortlessly and Music was the name given to the informant as he brings a guitar during the interview session. Lastly, Chatterbox was the name given to the participant because during the interview, she is very lively and expressive in nature. She highlights her ability to engage in lively discussions and keep the conversation flowing, she is very playful that she embraces her talkative side, that's why the researcher called her Chatterbox.

The participants were chosen based on their experience, The participants were chosen based on their insights and perceptions about the novice teachers teaching students with special needs, they were recognized and chosen according to the criteria of the research study, and their participation was confirmed by their own personal declaration. The in-depth interviews were done face-to-face at a time that was convenient for each informant. The participants' data was recorded by the researcher using smartphones, which is a crucial step in ensuring the study's validity and reliability.

Categorizing of Data

After the interview, recorded conversations were transcribed, translated, and subsequently analyzed. The researcher initiated the analysis through the process of coding. Coding was the technique of arranging resources into pieces of text before giving meaning to the information. The coding technique was utilized to provide a description of the set of people as well as the categories of themes to be analyzed. These topics were used to help form a broad description of the phenomena under investigation.

In order to classify the data, the major themes were given in order to address each research question. To give a detailed overview, the study's themes were thoroughly discussed and elaborated to provide a vivid description. Then came the conclusion and verification, which is the part of the investigation when the initial concepts and patterns regarding the findings are established (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

In order to add trustworthiness to the study, the researcher made note of the dimensions of credibility, dependability, transferability, and confirmability. To address credibility, member verification was carried out in addition to the triangulation approach. This was accomplished by providing copies of the interview transcript to participants so they may remark on it and certify to its authenticity. None of the informants had yet voiced any criticism of the transcript or offered any contradictory information. They all put their signatures on the participant verification form to indicate that they said yes. The triangulation of the study was made possible by the fact that it contained readings from participants and linked works, or more than two sources (Creswell & Miller, 2000).

To ensure dependability and confirmability, the researcher provided an audit trail. This trail was established with the purpose of allowing the research review panel to validate the results, assumptions, and conjectures put forth in the study (Carcary, 2009).

In terms of transferability, the researcher stated from the beginning that the results could not be generalized because these views were based only on the participants' own experiences in the indicated localities. Nonetheless, the researchers agreed that when the credibility, confirmability, and dependability of a qualitative case study are assured, then transferability is addressed as well (Klein & Myers, 1999)

Research Question No. 1: What are the lived experiences encountered by novice teachers teaching students with special needs?

This question aimed to explore and understand the lived experiences of novice teachers teaching students with special needs. It sought to uncover the challenges, successes, and overall journey of these teachers as they navigate their less than 1-year experiences in their profession. In the responses of the participants, there were four emerging themes that the researcher has found. The following themes were: Dealing with Challenges in Interaction with Students with Special Needs, implementing teaching strategies to meet the needs of students, Effectiveness in Adapting Teaching, and Using Diverse Instructional Materials.

Table 2. *The lived Experiences of Novice teachers teaching students with special needs*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Dealing with Challenges in Interaction with Students with Special Needs	"I usually employ patience and understanding when interacting with students who may have difficulty processing information or expressing themselves."- IDI-02
	"In my interaction with students with special needs, being sensitive to their requirements is important. I provide them with the proper support in their tasks and value their abilities. I use visual aids and multisensory materials to help them better understand the lessons. I also communicate with their parents and teachers regarding any changes or needs in their learning, with the aim of providing a positive experience for their development." - IDI-04
	"I recently came across an interesting article about how new SPED teachers are emphasizing the use of positive

<p>Implementing teaching strategies to meet the needs of students</p>	<p>reinforcement to build self-esteem and encourage desired behaviors in their students. I believe that fostering a positive and supportive learning environment is crucial for the success of students with special needs.” IDI-06 “In my interactions with students with special needs, I show care for their situation. I use simple words and short sentences to make the instructions easy to understand. I listen to them attentively and provide appropriate responses. I praise their successes and offer support to foster a positive self-view. I also use visual aids like pictures and flashcards to help them better understand tasks. In this way, I create a positive environment in the classroom.”- IDI-14 “Interaction is still the same with the other student talk to them politely with respect and also discipline them as well if it is necessary. Let them feel that the teacher can be their friend. Using sign language to the Hearing-Impaired students.” - IDI-01 “I vary my instructional methods and materials to meet the diverse needs of students.” - IDI-02 “By giving them activities within their level and give them considerations in every task.” -IDI-03 “In my interaction with students with special needs, being sensitive to their requirements is important. I provide them with the proper support in their tasks and value their abilities. I use visual aids and multisensory materials to help them better understand the lessons. I also communicate with their parents and teachers regarding any changes or needs in their learning, with the aim of providing a positive experience for their development.” - IDI-04 “I always try to break down complex concepts into smaller, more manageable steps to ensure that you understand them better. I believe that by simplifying things, we can make learning more enjoyable and effective.” - IDI-06</p>
<p>Effectiveness in Adapting Teaching Methods for Students with Special Needs.</p>	<p>“Teaching strategies will depend on what skill do the learners need to improve and develop. Maximize the use of assistive technology and manipulative toys to have an interesting and fun in learning.” - IDI-01 Adapting lesson plans on the fly to meet unexpected student needs can be difficult. I make it a point make it a point to find the right balance between providing structure and allowing for flexibility.” - IDI-02 It is really hard to adapt to students with special needs because I need to consider many things in dealing with them for them to be able to learn with other students. On the other hand, amidst the negatives and hardships in adopting. It is really a pleasure for me if students can learn and show interest in my lesson despite of the challenges, I have faced on dealing with them.” - IDI-03 In my view, there are many challenges and successes in adapting my teaching for students with special needs. A major challenge is the diversity of their needs and abilities. I experience success when I see students making progress, but there are times when my methods are not effective. Despite the challenges, their development inspires me to continuously improve my teaching for their benefit.” - IDI-04 I have come to realize that not every learning approach is effective for everyone. It's important to have an open mind and be willing to adapt to new methods when necessary. When I see my students’, confidence grow as they master skills through individualized approaches, it reinforces the importance of personalized learning.” - IDI-06</p>
<p>Using Diverse Instructional Materials</p>	<p>“To effectively adapt your teaching methods for students with special needs, it's important to understand each learner’s unique disabilities, history, family background, and financial situation. This awareness helps you address their specific needs. Engage with parents through interviews, observations, home visits, and assessments. Encourage them to let their children socialize with peers, rather than keeping them hidden away. This exposure can greatly benefit their development.” - IDI-01 I employ hands- on materials that students can interact with to learn concepts puzzles, blocks etc.” - IDI-02 In teaching students with special needs, I use various types of learning materials to facilitate and broaden their understanding, such as visual aids, adaptive technology, and modified worksheets.” - IDI-04 I think it is great that there are hands-on learning experiences available for our learners. These types of learning activities can be effective in teaching students with special needs.” - IDI-06 Assistive Technology, Hearing Aide for the Hearing Impaired, Braille for the Visually Impaired and for the Transition Program- Oven, Baking Tools, Sewing Machine, Steamer, Blender or any other Cooking Materials. Manipulative Toys, Clay, Blocks, Math Bus, Sorting Toys.” - IDI-01 “In teaching students with special needs, I use various materials to make learning easier. These include visual aids like pictures and flashcards to demonstrate concepts. I also use manipulatives like blocks to help them understand numbers. In addition, I use adapted texts and audio recordings for students who struggle with reading or hearing. Through these materials, I aim to help students achieve their learning goals.” -IDI-14</p>

Dealing with Challenges in Interaction with Students with Special Needs

For a novice teacher, "Dealing with Challenges in Interaction with Students with Special Needs" involves learning to understand and accommodate the diverse needs of students with disabilities. It requires familiarizing oneself with individualized education plans (IEPs) and seeking guidance from experienced colleagues and special education professionals. Adapting teaching methods to cater to different learning styles and abilities within the classroom is essential. Creating a supportive and inclusive environment where all students feel valued and included is a priority. Effective communication with students, their families, and other professionals is crucial for providing the necessary support. Novice teachers may face challenges in managing behavior and addressing unique needs, but with dedication and ongoing professional development, they can enhance their skills and create a positive learning environment for all students, including those with special needs.

According to Mr. Smile (pseudonym), he mentioned that learned the importance of employing patience and understanding when interacting with students who may face challenges in processing information or expressing themselves. This means taking the time to listen attentively to their needs and concerns, and offering support and encouragement as they navigate their learning journey. It's crucial to create a safe and supportive environment where students feel comfortable expressing themselves and asking for help when needed. By showing empathy and understanding, I aim to build trust and rapport with all my students, fostering a positive and inclusive classroom atmosphere where everyone can thrive. As he said that:

"I usually employ patience and understanding when interacting with students who may have difficulty processing information or expressing themselves". (IDI-02)

Furthermore, Sunflower (pseudonym) she mentioned the importance of being sensitive to the unique needs of students with special needs and demonstrating understanding and care in my interactions with them. It's crucial for me to provide them with the proper support and assistance they require to succeed academically and socially. This involves valuing their abilities and efforts and utilizing various strategies such as visual aids and multisensory materials to facilitate their understanding of lessons. Additionally, I understand the significance of maintaining close communication with their parents and other teachers to ensure that any changes or specific needs are addressed effectively. By prioritizing the well-being and development of students with special needs in this way, I strive to create a positive learning experience for them and support their overall growth and success. As she said that:

"Sa pakikipag-ugnayan ko sa mga estudyanteng may espesyal na pangangailangan, pinahalagahan ko ang pag-unawa at suporta. Gumagamit ako ng visual aids at multisensory materials para mas madaling maunawaan ang mga aralin. Nakikipag-ugnayan din ako sa mga magulang at guro upang ipaalam ang mga pagbabago sa pag-aaral, layunin kong bigyan sila ng positibong karanasan at tulong sa pag-unlad." (IDI 04)

(In my interactions with students with special needs, I value understanding and support. I use visual aids and multisensory materials to make lessons easier to understand. I also communicate with their parents and teachers to inform them of changes in their learning, aiming to provide a positive experience and assistance in their development.)

Moreover, Mayumi (pseudonym), she emphasizing the use of positive reinforcement to build self-esteem and encourage desired behaviors in their students. This approach resonates with me because I strongly believe that fostering a positive and supportive learning environment is crucial for the success of students with special needs. By focusing on positive reinforcement, teachers can help students develop confidence in their abilities and feel motivated to engage in learning activities. Creating a supportive atmosphere where students feel valued, encouraged, and respected not only enhances their academic progress but also contributes to their overall well-being and sense of belonging in the classroom. Therefore, as a novice teacher, I aspire to incorporate these principles into my interactions with students with special needs to promote their growth and success. As she said that:

"I recently came across an interesting article about how new SPED teachers are emphasizing the use of positive reinforcement to build self-esteem and encourage desired behaviors in their students. I believe that fostering a positive and supportive learning environment is crucial for the success of students with special needs". IDI-06.

Additionally, Chatterbox (pseudonym) she highlighted demonstrating compassion and understanding towards their individual situations. I recognize the importance of using simple language and short sentences to ensure that my instructions are easy for them to comprehend. When students communicate with me, I give them my full attention and provide appropriate responses to validate their thoughts and feelings. Moreover, I make a conscious effort to praise their successes and efforts, fostering a positive outlook on themselves and their abilities. Building trust and providing support are essential components of my approach, as I believe they contribute to students' overall well-being and confidence. These tools help students better understand tasks and classroom routines, making the learning process more accessible and engaging for them. By incorporating these methods of interaction into my teaching practice, I strive to maintain a positive and inclusive environment in the classroom where everyone feels accepted and valued for who they are. As she said that:

"Sa pakikipag-ugnayan ko sa mga estudyanteng may espesyal na pangangailangan, ipinapakita ko ang malasakit sa kanilang kalagayan. Gumagamit ako ng simpleng salita at maikling pangungusap para madaling maunawaan ang mga instruksyon. Pinakikinggan ko sila ng maayos at binibigyan ng tamang tugon. Pinupuri ko ang kanilang mga tagumpay at nagbibigay ng suporta para sa positibong pananaw sa kanilang sarili. Gumagamit din ako ng mga visual na suporta tulad ng larawan at flashcards para mas madali nilang maunawaan ang mga gawain. Sa ganitong paraan, nalilikha ko ang isang positibong kapaligiran sa silid-aralan". (IDI-14)

(In my interactions with students with special needs, I show care for their situation. I use simple words and short sentences to make the instructions easy to understand. I listen to them attentively and provide appropriate responses. I praise their successes and offer support to foster a positive self-view. I also use visual aids like pictures and flashcards to help them better understand tasks. In this way, I create a positive environment in the classroom.)

Likewise, Art (pseudonym) she highlighted that interactions with the students with special needs in a manner consistent with how I interact with all students. I believe in treating them with politeness and respect, while also maintaining appropriate discipline when necessary. It's important for students to feel valued and respected, regardless of their individual challenges or abilities. By demonstrating

respect and establishing clear boundaries, I aim to create a positive and supportive classroom environment where all students feel included and accepted. Furthermore, I recognize the importance of fostering a friendly and supportive relationship with students, where they feel comfortable approaching me for help or guidance. By letting students know that the teacher can also be their friend, I hope to create a sense of trust and rapport that enhances their learning experience. Additionally, for hearing-impaired students, I understand the importance of using sign language to facilitate communication. This ensures that all students can actively participate in classroom discussions and activities, regardless of their hearing abilities. By incorporating sign language into my interactions, I strive to create an inclusive environment where every student feels valued and understood. As she said that:

"Interaction is still the same with the other student talk to them politely with respect and also discipline them as well if it is necessary. Let them feel that the teacher can be their friend. Using sign language to the Hearing-Impaired students". (IDI-1)

Implementing teaching strategies to meet the needs of students

Implementing teaching strategies tailored to meet the diverse needs of students is essential for fostering inclusive and effective learning environments. Teachers can employ various methods such as differentiated instruction, which adapts content and activities to accommodate different learning styles and abilities within the classroom. Utilizing technology integration can also enhance accessibility and engagement, providing opportunities for personalized instruction and flexible learning pathways. Moreover, collaborative learning approaches promote peer interaction and cooperation, enabling students to learn from one another and develop essential social and communication skills. By incorporating these strategies alongside assessment for learning techniques and reflective practices, educators can create dynamic and supportive learning experiences that cater to the individual needs and strengths of all students, fostering their academic growth and success.

According, Mr. Smile (pseudonym) he adapting their teaching approach to cater to the diverse needs of students is crucial in ensuring effective learning outcomes. I incorporate a range of instructional methods and materials to accommodate different learning styles, abilities, and preferences within the classroom. This might involve using visual aids, hands-on activities, group discussions, or multimedia resources to engage students and facilitate understanding. By varying my approach, I can better address the individual needs of each student, creating a more inclusive and supportive learning environment. This flexibility allows me to reach students with diverse backgrounds, experiences, and learning profiles, ultimately enhancing their learning experiences and academic success. As he said that:

"I vary my instructional methods and materials to meet the diverse needs of students". (IDI-02)

Furthermore, Chinita (pseudonym) she suggests a method of approach or strategy aimed at supporting individuals, likely in an educational or developmental context. This approach involves tailoring activities to match the proficiency or capability level of the individuals involved. Additionally, it emphasizes the importance of providing considerations or accommodations in every task to ensure that each individual can fully participate and engage according to their needs and abilities. Essentially, it advocates for a personalized and inclusive approach to learning or task completion, where everyone's unique strengths and challenges are taken into account. As she said that:

"By giving them activities within their level and give them considerations in every task". (IDI-03)

Moreover, Sunflower (pseudonym) she implements diverse teaching strategies to support my students with special needs effectively. Initially, I customize my lessons and tasks according to each student's unique needs and capabilities. Utilizing visual aids and multisensory materials further enhances their comprehension of concepts. Additionally, I ensure clear instructions are provided, coupled with positive reinforcement to bolster their confidence. Maintaining open communication with both parents and fellow educators is crucial for fostering cooperation and ensuring holistic support for the students' learning journey. Through these methods, I aim to deliver comprehensive and empathetic teaching to meet the diverse needs of my students. As she said that:

"Sa pakikipag-ugnayan ko sa mga estudyanteng may espesyal na pangangailangan, mahalaga ang pagiging sensitibo sa kanilang mga pangangailangan. Binibigyan ko sila ng tamang suporta sa kanilang gawain at pinapahalagahan ang kanilang mga kakayahan. Gumagamit ako ng mga visual aids at multisensory materials para mas madali nilang maunawaan ang mga aralin. Nakikipag-ugnayan din ako sa kanilang mga magulang at guro para sa mga pagbabago o pangangailangan sa kanilang pag-aaral, layunin kong magbigay ng positibong karanasan sa kanilang pag-unlad". (IDI-04)

(In my interaction with students with special needs, being sensitive to their requirements is important. I provide them with the proper support in their tasks and value their abilities. I use visual aids and multisensory materials to help them better understand the lessons. I also communicate with their parents and teachers regarding any changes or needs in their learning, with the aim of providing a positive experience for their development.)

Additionally, Mayumi (pseudonym) she highlighted a teaching approach that prioritizes breaking down complex ideas into smaller, easier-to-understand components. By simplifying concepts, the goal is to enhance comprehension and make the learning process more enjoyable and effective. This strategy acknowledges that overwhelming students with complex information can hinder understanding, and instead advocates for a gradual, step-by-step approach to learning. Ultimately, the aim is to create a supportive and accessible learning environment where students feel empowered to grasp challenging concepts at their own pace. As she said that:

"I always try to break down complex concepts into smaller, more manageable steps to ensure that you understand them better. I believe that by simplifying things, we can make learning more enjoyable and effective". (IDI-06)

Likewise, Arts (pseudonym) she adaptability of teaching strategies based on the specific skills that learners need to enhance and cultivate. It emphasizes the importance of leveraging assistive technology and manipulative toys to inject excitement and engagement into the learning process. By tailoring instructional methods to address the unique needs of learners and integrating interactive tools, the aim is to foster an enjoyable and dynamic learning environment. This approach acknowledges the potential of innovative tools and techniques to enhance comprehension and retention while ensuring that learning remains both enriching and enjoyable for students. As she said that:

"Teaching strategies will depend on what skill do the learners need to improve and develop. Maximize the use of assistive technology and manipulative toys to have an interesting and fun in learning". (IDI-01)

Effectiveness in Adapting Teaching Methods for Students with Special Needs.

Effectiveness in adapting teaching methods for students with special needs hinges on personalized approaches tailored to individual requirements. By understanding each student's strengths, challenges, and learning styles, educators can modify instructional strategies accordingly. Implementing a diverse range of techniques, such as multisensory learning, visual aids, and differentiated instruction, ensures accessibility and engagement for all learners. Regular assessment and feedback help refine teaching methods to meet evolving needs, fostering an inclusive and supportive learning environment. Collaboration with parents, specialists, and colleagues further enhances effectiveness by drawing on collective expertise and resources. Ultimately, successful adaptation of teaching methods empowers students with special needs to thrive academically, socially, and emotionally.

According to Mr. Smile (pseudonym) he highlighted the challenge of adapting lesson plans spontaneously to address unforeseen student needs. The speaker emphasizes the importance of striking a delicate balance between maintaining structure and accommodating flexibility. This approach recognizes the necessity of having a framework in place while remaining open to adjusting plans in response to students' immediate requirements. By finding this equilibrium, educators can ensure that lessons remain purposeful and coherent while also allowing space for spontaneous adaptations that enhance student learning and engagement. As he said that:

"Adapting lesson plans on the fly to meet unexpected student needs can be difficult. I make it a point make it a point to find the right balance between providing structure and allowing for flexibility". (IDI-02)

Furthermore, Chinita (pseudonym) she reflects the complexity of adapting to students with special needs, acknowledging the multitude of factors that must be considered to facilitate their integration with other students. Despite the challenges involved, the speaker finds fulfillment and satisfaction when students demonstrate learning and interest in their lessons. This highlights the intrinsic reward that comes from overcoming obstacles and witnessing the positive impact of inclusive teaching practices. It underscores the educator's dedication to fostering an inclusive environment where all students can thrive, despite the difficulties encountered along the way. As she said that:

"It is really hard to adapt to students with special needs because I need to consider many things in dealing with them for them to be able to learn with other students. On the other hand, amidst the negatives and hardships in adopting. It is really a pleasure for me if students can learn and show interest in my lesson despite of the challenges, I've faced on dealing with them". (IDI-03)

Moreover, Sunflower (pseudonym) she provides a balanced perspective on the challenges and successes encountered when adjusting teaching methods for students with special needs. It acknowledges the diverse range of needs and abilities among students, which presents a significant challenge for teachers. Despite this, the speaker finds success in witnessing progress and improvement in students' skills and knowledge when adjustments are made to teaching methods. However, there are occasions when these adaptations may not yield the desired outcomes, highlighting the necessity of being innovative and analytical in teaching approaches. Nonetheless, the successes achieved in enhancing students' abilities and development serve as sources of hope and inspiration, driving the continuous improvement of teaching methods for the benefit and success of the students. As she said that:

"Sa aking pananaw, maraming hamon at tagumpay sa pag-aangkop ng aking pagtuturo para sa mga estudyanteng may espesyal na pangangailangan. Isang malaking hamon ang pagkakaiba-iba ng kanilang mga pangangailangan at kakayahan. Nakakaranas ako ng tagumpay kapag nakikita kong umuunlad ang mga estudyante, ngunit may mga pagkakataong hindi naging epektibo ang aking mga paraan. Sa kabila ng mga hamon, ang kanilang pag-unlad ang nagbibigay sa akin ng inspirasyon na patuloy na pagbutihin ang aking pagtuturo para sa kanilang kapakanan". (IDI-04)

(In my view, there are many challenges and successes in adapting my teaching for students with special needs. A major challenge is the diversity of their needs and abilities. I experience success when I see students making progress, but there are times when my methods are not effective. Despite the challenges, their development inspires me to continuously improve my teaching for their benefit.)

Additionally, Mayumi (pseudonym) she recognize that not every learning approach suits every individual. It emphasizes the necessity of remaining open-minded and adaptable to new methods when required. Witnessing students' confidence flourish as they excel using personalized approaches reinforces the significance of tailoring learning experiences to individual needs. This highlights a commitment

to fostering a dynamic and inclusive learning environment where each student can thrive based on their unique strengths and preferences. As she said that:

"I've come to realize that not every learning approach is effective for everyone. It's important to have an open mind and be willing to adapt to new methods when necessary. When I see my students', confidence grow as they master skills through individualized approaches, it reinforces the importance of personalized learning". (IDI-06)

Likewise, Art (Pseudonym) she highlighted the importance of perceiving challenges and successes in adapting teaching methods for students with special needs through a comprehensive understanding of each learner's unique circumstances. It stresses the significance of knowing the various disabilities present, as well as factors such as family background, living situation, parental involvement, and financial status. By gaining insight into these aspects, teachers can effectively address the needs and limitations of each student through methods such as interviews, observations, home visits, and assessments. Furthermore, it advocates for encouraging parents to promote socialization opportunities for their children with special needs, emphasizing the importance of exposure and interaction beyond the confines of the family environment. As she said that:

"To effectively adapt your teaching methods for students with special needs, it's important to understand each learner's unique disabilities, history, family background, and financial situation. This awareness helps you address their specific needs. Engage with parents through interviews, observations, home visits, and assessments. Encourage them to let their children socialize with peers, rather than keeping them hidden away. This exposure can greatly benefit their development". (IDI-01)

Using Diverse Instructional Materials

Utilizing diverse instructional materials enriches the learning experience by catering to different learning styles and preferences. Incorporating a variety of materials such as textbooks, videos, interactive online resources, and hands-on manipulatives enhances engagement and comprehension. Furthermore, diverse materials provide opportunities for students to explore content from multiple perspectives, fostering critical thinking and deeper understanding. By embracing a range of instructional materials, educators can create dynamic and inclusive learning environments that cater to the diverse needs and interests of their students.

According to Mr. Smile he emphasizes the use of hands-on materials, such as puzzles and blocks, to facilitate student learning through interaction. By employing tactile and manipulative resources, educators provide students with opportunities to actively engage with and explore concepts in a concrete and tangible manner. This approach fosters experiential learning, allowing students to physically manipulate objects to better understand abstract ideas. Additionally, hands-on materials cater to diverse learning styles and promote skill development, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities. Overall, incorporating these interactive tools enhances student participation, comprehension, and retention of key concepts. As he said that:

"I employ hands-on materials that students can interact with to learn concepts puzzles, blocks etc". (IDI-02)

Furthermore, Sunflower (pseudonym) she employs a range of learning materials designed to enhance their understanding and facilitate learning. These include visual aids, which help convey information through images, diagrams, and other visual representations to make concepts more accessible. Additionally, I utilize adaptive technology to accommodate different learning styles and address individual needs, ensuring that all students can engage with the material effectively. Modified worksheets are also utilized to provide tailored content that aligns with students' abilities, allowing them to practice and reinforce key concepts at their own pace. By incorporating these diverse learning materials, I aim to create an inclusive and supportive learning environment that promotes the success of students with special needs. As she said that:

"Sa pagtuturo sa mga estudyanteng may espesyal na pangangailangan, ginagamit ko ang iba't ibang uri ng learning materials upang mapadali at mapalawak ang kanilang pag-unawa tulad ng visual aids, adaptive technology and modified worksheets". (IDI-04)

(In teaching students with special needs, I use various types of learning materials to facilitate and broaden their understanding, such as visual aids, adaptive technology, and modified worksheets.)

Moreover, Mayumi (pseudonym) she expressing appreciation for hands-on learning experiences, especially for learners with special needs, indicates recognition of the effectiveness of interactive and tactile educational approaches. By acknowledging the value of hands-on activities, the speaker highlights their potential to engage students with diverse learning styles and abilities. This approach fosters experiential learning, allowing students to actively participate and explore concepts in a tangible way, which can be particularly beneficial for those with special needs. Overall, embracing hands-on learning experiences reflects a commitment to providing inclusive and effective educational opportunities for all learners. As she said that:

"I think it's great that there are hands-on learning experiences available for our learners. These types of learning activities can be effective in teaching students with special needs". (IDI-06)

Additionally, Art (pseudonym) she enumerates various assistive technologies and materials utilized to support students with different needs in an educational setting. For the hearing impaired, hearing aids are mentioned to aid auditory comprehension. Braille is highlighted as a resource for visually impaired students to access written information. In the transition program, practical tools like ovens, sewing machines, and cooking materials are listed, emphasizing hands-on skill development. Manipulative toys such as clay,

blocks, and sorting toys are included to facilitate sensory learning and motor skill development. Additionally, the mention of a "Math Bus" suggests interactive educational tools to engage students in mathematical concepts. Overall, these resources cater to diverse learning needs and promote inclusive learning environments. As she said that:

"Assistive Technology, Hearing Aide for the Hearing Impaired, Braille for the Visually Impaired and for the Transition Program- Oven, Baking Tools, Sewing Machine, Steamer, Blender or any other Cooking Materials. Manipulative Toys, Clay, Blocks, Math Bus, Sorting Toys". (IDI-01)

Likewise, Chatterbox (pseudonym) she employs a diverse range of materials tailored to enhance their learning and comprehension of concepts. Visual aids, such as pictures, graphics, and flashcards, are utilized to provide visual representation and reinforce understanding. Hands-on manipulatives, including blocks and manipulative values, are incorporated to facilitate tactile learning and deepen understanding of numerical concepts. Adapted texts and audio recordings are also utilized to accommodate students with reading or hearing impairments, ensuring equitable access to information. By employing these varied materials, I demonstrate a steadfast commitment to supporting students with special needs in attaining their learning objectives, fostering an inclusive and supportive learning environment. As she said that:

"Sa pagtuturo ng mga estudyanteng may espesyal na pangangailangan, gumagamit ako ng iba't ibang materyales para mas mapadali ang kanilang pag-aaral. Kabilang dito ang mga visual aids tulad ng mga larawan at flashcards para ipakita ang mga konsepto. Gumagamit din ako ng mga manipulatives tulad ng blocks para tulungan silang maunawaan ang mga numero. Bukod dito, gumagamit ako ng adaptadong mga teksto at audio recordings para sa mga estudyanteng nahihirapan sa pagbasa o pandinig. Sa pamamagitan ng mga materyales na ito, nais kong tulungan ang mga estudyante na maabot ang kanilang mga layunin". (IDI-014)

(In teaching students with special needs, I use various materials to make learning easier. These include visual aids like pictures and flashcards to demonstrate concepts. I also use manipulatives like blocks to help them understand numbers. In addition, I use adapted texts and audio recordings for students who struggle with reading or hearing. Through these materials, I aim to help students achieve their learning goals.)

Research Question No. 2: How do novice teachers cope with the challenges in teaching students with special needs?

This question aimed to explore and understand the novice teachers cope with challenges in teaching students with special needs by seeking support and guidance from experienced colleagues and mentors. They actively engage in professional development opportunities to enhance their knowledge and skills in inclusive teaching practices. Additionally, novice teachers collaborate with special education professionals, parents, and other stakeholders to develop individualized education plans and strategies tailored to meet students' unique needs. They continuously reflect on their teaching practices, adapt instructional approaches, and provide ongoing encouragement and support to students, fostering a positive and inclusive learning environment. Through perseverance, empathy, and a willingness to learn, novice teachers navigate the challenges of teaching students with special needs with dedication and resilience. In the responses of the participants, there were four emerging themes that the researcher has found. The following themes were: Individualized Support and Differentiation of students with special needs, Building Rapport and Relationships, Collaboration and Professional Development, Flexibility and Adaptability and Strong Motivation from One's Students.

Table 3. *Coping Strategies of Novice teachers in teaching students with Special Needs*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Individualized Support and Differentiation of students with special needs	<p>"I usually ask for help from other special education teacher to help me in handling students with special needs." - IDI-02</p> <p>"In addressing the needs of my students with special needs, I use various strategies. First, I assess their abilities through observation and evaluation. Then, I create teaching plans that are tailored to their needs. I use multisensory materials and visual aids to help them understand concepts more easily. Additionally, I incorporate adaptive technologies and other support tools in their learning. I provide activities based on their interests to maintain their attention. I also value communication with their parents and guardians for feedback and collaboration in teaching." -IDI-04</p> <p>"I create variations in content, process, product, and learning environment to cater to different learning styles and abilities. This might involve offering graphic organizers for visual learners, providing audiobooks for struggling readers or allowing students to demonstrate mastery through creative projects." -IDI-06</p> <p>"Strategies occurs depending on what is the needs of a learner, based on the Individual Educational Plan (IEP) constructed by the teacher with the permission and agreement of the parent as well. The same approach to the regular students, SPED teachers do have targets too." -IDI-01</p> <p>"I use various materials to assist students with special needs. This includes visual aids like pictures and flashcards, manipulatives such as blocks for numerical concepts, and adapted texts and audio recordings for easier access to information. With these resources, my goal is to make their learning easier and help them achieve their objectives." -IDI-14</p>
Building Rapport and Relationships	<p>"I build positive relationships through praise, encouragement, and celebrating successes." -IDI-02</p> <p>"Talk to them politely and ask them from time to time on how they are during their class." -IDI-03</p> <p>"In navigating and establishing rapport with students with special needs, it is important to show understanding and love. First, I demonstrate my interest in their situation by listening to their needs. I regularly communicate with</p>

	<p>them and ask how I can help in their learning. Second, I also reach out to their parents and caregivers. Through good communication, I gain their trust and cooperation in teaching their children.” -IDI-04</p> <p>“I have seen firsthand the positive impact that predictable routines and visual schedules can have on students. It helps them feel more comfortable and confident in the classroom, leading to a more positive and productive learning experience.” -IDI-06</p> <p>“I do establish rapport to the Learners with Special Needs (LSeN) through the coordination with the experts especially in their medical assessment so that the teacher will do our part to address their needs. Let the children feel that you are the trusted person whom they can lean on and along with.” -IDI-01</p>
Collaboration and Professional Development	<p>“I collaborate with special education teachers to deliver instruction jointly.” -IDI-02</p> <p>“Through asking advice and strategies on how to enhance the educational experiences of students with special needs.” -IDI-03</p> <p>“To improve the experience of students with special needs, collaboration with other professionals is essential. Through teamwork, we can create individualized plans and support for each student. We can also share knowledge and skills to create a vibrant learning environment that meets their needs. Effective coordination is key to helping every student reach their potential in education.” -IDI-04</p> <p>“I regularly communicate with other professionals about student progress, successes, and areas needing additional support.” -IDI-06</p> <p>“I collaborate with other special education through the professionals’ personnel for being have a good interaction to the students with special education.” -IDI-01</p>
Flexibility and Adaptability	<p>“I focus on clear and measurable learning objectives that can be achieved through different instructional approaches.” -IDI-02</p> <p>“I can make on the spot revisions and adjustments in my lesson plan if there are challenges encountered with them during the lesson.” -IDI-03</p> <p>“As a new teacher, it is important to be adaptable in your plans and teaching methods for students with special needs. When you encounter challenges, be open to change. Review and assess your lesson plans to identify what needs to be adjusted. You may need to add visual aids, manipulatives, or other materials to help students better understand the lessons. It is also essential to be sensitive and understanding of their needs. By focusing on their limitations and continually adjusting your teaching, you can help strengthen their growth and success in learning.” -IDI-04</p> <p>“I prepare detailed lesson plans but remain flexible to adjust them based on student needs during the lesson.” IDI06</p> <p>“Lesson planning is one of our tools in teaching. In our field, I used the weekly learning plan as our guide in teaching, in which the targeted task and topic were indicated and the objectives as well. In the Special Education Program, it requires the Individual Educational Plan (IEP) wherein the strengths and weaknesses of each learner was stated and this is where we record their improvements as well.” -IDI-01</p>
Strong Motivation from One’s Students	<p>“Witnessing students with special needs learn, grow and achieve their full potential is already a rewarding experience.” -IDI-02</p> <p>“The connections I form with my students are truly special. Seeing their growth in confidence and independence is incredibly motivating.” -IDI-06</p> <p>“It is already satisfying to watch special needs students develop, learn, and reach their full potential.” -IDI-07</p> <p>“I motivated to teach students with special needs because I have a passion to give them knowledge in able the to survive things in a near future without the needs of help with another person.” -IDI-13</p> <p>“I inspire and drives me to continue teaching students with special needs is their progress and success. It is heartwarming and fulfilling to witness their growth and development as they learn. Being part of their journey towards achieving their dreams and potential brings me joy and purpose in my role as a teacher. Additionally, the feeling of being able to help and positively impact the lives of others is also a significant motivation for me.” IDI14</p>

Individualized Support and Differentiation of Students with Special Needs

Individualized support and differentiation of students with special needs means providing personalized assistance tailored to each student’s unique learning style and abilities, while differentiation involves adapting teaching methods, materials, and assessments to accommodate diverse needs within the classroom, ensuring that all students have the opportunity to thrive academically and socially. Individualized support and differentiation of students with special needs involve tailoring instruction and resources to meet the specific needs and abilities of each learner. This approach recognizes that students have diverse learning styles, strengths, and challenges. By providing personalized support, educators can address academic, social, and emotional needs effectively, ensuring that every student can succeed. Differentiation encompasses adjusting the content, process, and assessment to accommodate varying levels of readiness, interests, and learning preferences, promoting engagement and understanding for all students. Through individualized support and differentiation, educators create inclusive learning environments where every student can thrive and reach their full potential.

According to Mr. Smile (pseudonym) he statements reflects a proactive approach by seeking assistance from other special education teachers to effectively support students with special needs. Collaborating with colleagues who have expertise in special education allows for sharing knowledge, strategies, and resources. By leveraging the collective experience and insights of fellow educators, the teacher can gain valuable support in addressing the diverse needs of students with special needs. This collaborative approach fosters a supportive professional environment and enhances the teacher's ability to provide comprehensive and effective support to all students. As she said that:

"I usually ask for help from other special education teacher to help me in handling students with special needs". (IDI-02)

Furthermore, Sunflower (pseudonym) she emphasizing that comprehensive approach to addressing the individual learning needs of students with special needs. The teacher begins by assessing each student's needs and capabilities through careful observation and evaluation. Based on this assessment, personalized teaching plans are developed to cater to their specific requirements. Utilizing multisensory materials and visual aids enhances their comprehension of concepts, while adaptive technologies and supportive aids further support their learning process. Additionally, the teacher ensures activities align with students' interests to sustain their engagement and enthusiasm for learning. Close communication with parents and caregivers is emphasized to gather insights, suggestions, and feedback, fostering collaboration and ensuring a holistic approach to teaching and support. Overall, this approach reflects a commitment to providing tailored and effective instruction that meets the diverse needs of students with special needs. As she said that:

"Sa pagtugon sa mga pangangailangan ng aking mga estudyanteng may espesyal na pangangailangan, gumagamit ako ng iba't ibang estratehiya. Una, sinusuri ko ang kanilang kakayahan sa pamamagitan ng pag-observe at pag-evaluate. Pagkatapos, bumubuo ako ng mga plano ng pagtuturo na naaayon sa kanilang mga pangangailangan. Gumagamit ako ng mga multisensory materials at visual aids para mas madali nilang maunawaan ang mga konsepto. Pati na rin, gumagamit ako ng adaptive technologies at iba pang tulong sa kanilang pag-aaral. Nagbibigay ako ng mga aktibidad batay sa kanilang mga interes para mapanatili ang kanilang atensyon. Mahalaga rin sa akin ang pakikipag-ugnayan sa kanilang mga magulang at tagapag-alaga para sa feedback at kooperasyon sa pagtuturo". (IDI-4)

(In addressing the needs of my students with special needs, I use various strategies. First, I assess their abilities through observation and evaluation. Then, I create teaching plans that are tailored to their needs. I use multisensory materials and visual aids to help them understand concepts more easily. Additionally, I incorporate adaptive technologies and other support tools in their learning. I provide activities based on their interests to maintain their attention. I also value communication with their parents and guardians for feedback and collaboration in teaching.)

Moreover, Mayumi (pseudonym) she illustrates a commitment to differentiation by creating variations across content, process, product, and learning environment to accommodate diverse learning styles and abilities. For visual learners, graphic organizers are provided to enhance comprehension and organization of information. Struggling readers benefit from access to audiobooks, facilitating auditory learning and comprehension. Additionally, allowing students to demonstrate mastery through creative projects fosters engagement and allows for expression of understanding through alternative means. By implementing these varied approaches, educators ensure that all students can access and engage with the material effectively, promoting inclusivity and maximizing learning outcomes. As she said that:

"I create variations in content, process, product, and learning environment to cater to different learning styles and abilities. This might involve offering graphic organizers for visual learners, providing audiobooks for struggling readers or allowing students to demonstrate mastery through creative projects". (IDI-06)

Additionally, Art (pseudonym) she emphasizes the importance of tailoring strategies to meet the individual needs of learners, with guidance from the Individual Educational Plan (IEP) collaboratively developed by teachers and parents. It emphasizes the significance of parental involvement and agreement in the construction of the IEP, highlighting the collaborative nature of special education planning. Additionally, it acknowledges that special education teachers have specific targets and goals outlined in the IEP, similar to how regular education teachers have objectives for their students. This approach ensures that students with special needs receive personalized support and interventions aligned with their unique requirements, fostering their academic and overall development. As she said that:

"Strategies occurs depending on what is the needs of a learner, based on the Individual Educational Plan (IEP) constructed by the teacher with the permission and agreement of the parent as well. The same approach to the regular students, SPED teachers do have targets too". (IDI-01)

Likewise, Chatterbox (pseudonym) she addressing the individual learning needs of students with special needs, I implement a range of strategies. Firstly, I offer individualized teaching or training sessions tailored to their unique requirements and abilities. Secondly, I actively involve their families in the teaching process to ensure consistent support from home and alignment with their educational goals. Thirdly, I leverage technology by incorporating applications or programs containing specialized modules designed to meet their specific learning needs. Lastly, I design exercises aimed at strengthening their skills while also addressing any limitations they may encounter. Through these multifaceted approaches, I strive to create a supportive and inclusive learning environment that fosters the academic and personal development of each student with special needs. As she said that:

"Gumagamit ako ng iba't ibang materyales para tulungan ang mga estudyanteng may espesyal na pangangailangan. Kabilang dito ang mga visual aids tulad ng larawan at flashcards, manipulatives tulad ng blocks para sa mga numerikal na konsepto, at adaptadong teksto at audio recordings para sa mas madaling pag-access sa impormasyon. Sa mga ito, layunin kong mas mapadali ang kanilang pag-aaral at maabot ang kanilang mga layunin". (IDI-14)

(I use various materials to assist students with special needs. This includes visual aids like pictures and flashcards, manipulatives such

as blocks for numerical concepts, and adapted texts and audio recordings for easier access to information. With these resources, my goal is to make their learning easier and help them achieve their objectives.)

Building Rapport and Relationships

Building rapport and relationships in an educational setting involves establishing trust, mutual respect, and positive connections with students. This can be achieved through active listening, empathy, and genuine interest in their well-being. It also involves fostering open communication, creating a supportive environment, and showing appreciation for their individual strengths and contributions. Ultimately, building rapport and relationships lays the foundation for effective teaching and learning experiences, as it enhances student engagement, motivation, and overall success.

According to Mr. Smile (pseudonym) he consistently offering praise and encouragement, I create an atmosphere of positivity and support in which students feel valued and motivated to excel. Celebrating successes reinforces their accomplishments and boosts their confidence, strengthening our bond and enhancing their overall learning experience. This approach fosters a sense of trust and appreciation, laying the groundwork for meaningful relationships built on mutual respect and recognition of individual achievements. As he said that:

"I build positive relationships through praise, encouragement, and celebrating successes". (IDI-02)

Furthermore, Chinita (pseudonym) she maintaining polite communication and regularly checking in with students during class demonstrates care and concern for their well-being. By asking how they are and actively listening to their responses, I create a supportive and inclusive learning environment where students feel valued and understood. This approach fosters trust and open communication, strengthening our relationship and enhancing their overall experience in the classroom. As she said that:

"Talk to them politely and ask them from time to time on how they are during their class". (IDI-03)

Moreover, Mayumi (pseudonym) she establishing rapport with students with special needs involves prioritizing their well-being through understanding, care, and empathy. This is achieved by actively listening to their needs and feelings, engaging in regular conversations, and offering assistance with their studies. Additionally, collaborating with parents or caregivers through close communication helps to build trust and cooperation in supporting the child's education. Through these actions, a supportive and inclusive learning environment is fostered, catering to the unique needs of each student. As she said that:

"Sa pag-navigate at pag-establish ng rapport sa mga estudyanteng may espesyal na pangangailangan, mahalaga ang pagpapakita ng pag-unawa at pagmamahal. Una, ipinapakita ko ang interes ko sa kanilang kalagayan sa pamamagitan ng pakikinig sa kanilang mga pangangailangan. Regular akong nakikipag-usap sa kanila at nagtatanong kung paano ko sila matutulungan sa kanilang pag-aaral. Pangalawa, nilalapat ko rin ang mga magulang at tagapag-alaga. Sa magandang komunikasyon, nakakamit ko ang kanilang tiwala at kooperasyon sa pagtuturo sa kanilang mga anak". (IDI-04)

(In navigating and establishing rapport with students with special needs, it is important to show understanding and love. First, I demonstrate my interest in their situation by listening to their needs. I regularly communicate with them and ask how I can help in their learning. Second, I also reach out to their parents and caregivers. Through good communication, I gain their trust and cooperation in teaching their children.)

Additionally, Mayumi (pseudonym) she implementing predictable routines and visual schedules in the classroom has a profound positive impact on students. By providing structure and clarity, it helps students feel more at ease and confident, ultimately enhancing their learning experience. Predictable routines reduce anxiety and uncertainty, promoting a sense of stability and security within the classroom environment. Visual schedules aid in comprehension and organization, enabling students to navigate tasks and transitions more effectively. Overall, these strategies foster a more positive and productive learning atmosphere, contributing to the academic and emotional growth of students. As she said that:

"I have seen firsthand the positive impact that predictable routines and visual schedules can have on students. It helps them feel more comfortable and confident in the classroom, leading to a more positive and productive learning experience". (IDI-06)

Likewise, Art (pseudonym) she the importance of establishing rapport with learners with special needs (LSeN) by collaborating with medical experts for their assessment. This collaboration enables teachers to effectively address the specific needs of these learners. It emphasizes the significance of being a trusted figure whom the children can rely on for support and guidance. This approach aims to create a supportive environment where learners feel understood and cared for, fostering their engagement and learning. As she said that:

"I do establish rapport to the Learners with Special Needs (LSeN) through the coordination with the experts especially in their medical assessment so that the teacher will do our part to address their needs. Let the children feel that you are the trusted person whom they can lean on and along with". (IDI-01)

Collaboration and Professional Development

Collaboration in education involves working together with colleagues, administrators, and other stakeholders to achieve common goals

and enhance student learning. Through collaboration, educators share resources, ideas, and expertise to improve teaching practices and student outcomes. Professional development encompasses ongoing learning and growth opportunities that enable educators to enhance their knowledge, skills, and effectiveness in the classroom. By engaging in collaboration and professional development, educators stay current with best practices, adapt to changing educational needs, and continuously strive for excellence in their teaching profession.

According to Mr. Smile (pseudonym) he highlighted the collaborative approach taken by the speaker, who actively partners with special education teachers to deliver instruction collaboratively. By working together, educators can leverage their respective expertise and insights to meet the diverse needs of students more effectively. This collaborative effort ensures that instructional strategies are tailored to address the unique requirements of students with special needs, promoting inclusivity and maximizing learning outcomes. By fostering a supportive partnership, educators can create a cohesive and comprehensive learning environment that benefits all students. As he said that:

"I collaborate with special education teachers to deliver instruction jointly". (IDI-02)

Furthermore, Chinita (pseudonym) she emphasizes the proactive approach taken by the speaker in seeking advice and strategies to enhance the educational experiences of students with special needs. By actively seeking guidance, educators can gain valuable insights and resources to better support these students in their learning journey. Collaborating with colleagues, special education professionals, and other experts allows educators to access diverse perspectives and effective strategies tailored to meet the unique needs of students with special needs. This proactive engagement demonstrates a commitment to continuous improvement and ensures that students with special needs receive the necessary support and opportunities for optimal learning and growth. As she said that:

"Through asking advice and strategies on how to enhance the educational experiences of students with special needs". (IDI-03)

Moreover, Sunflower (pseudonym) she highlighted the importance of collaboration with other professionals in special education to enhance the educational experience of students with special needs. Through collaborative efforts, educators can develop individualized plans and support strategies tailored to each student's unique requirements. By sharing skills and knowledge, professionals can create a vibrant learning environment that addresses the diverse needs of all students effectively. Smooth coordination and collaboration are emphasized as essential elements in ensuring that each student can reach their highest potential in the field of education, promoting inclusivity and fostering success for all. As she said that:

"Para mapabuti ang karanasan ng mga mag-aaral na may espesyal na pangangailangan, mahalaga ang pakikipagtulungan sa ibang mga propesyonal. Sa pamamagitan ng pagtutulongan, makakabuo tayo ng mga indibidwal na plano at suporta para sa bawat mag-aaral. Maaari rin tayong magbahagi ng kaalaman at kasanayan upang lumikha ng masiglang kapaligiran ng pag-aaral na angkop sa kanilang mga pangangailangan. Ang maayos na koordinasyon ay susi upang matulungan ang bawat mag-aaral na maabot ang kanilang potensyal sa edukasyon". (IDI-04)

(To improve the experience of students with special needs, collaboration with other professionals is essential. Through teamwork, we can create individualized plans and support for each student. We can also share knowledge and skills to create a vibrant learning environment that meets their needs. Effective coordination is key to helping every student reach their potential in education.)

Additionally, Mayumi (pseudonym) she commitment to regular communication with other professionals regarding student progress, successes, and areas requiring additional support. By maintaining open lines of communication, educators can share valuable insights and observations to ensure a comprehensive understanding of each student's needs. Collaborative discussions allow for the identification of areas where students are excelling and where they may require additional assistance or interventions. This proactive approach fosters a supportive network of professionals working together to optimize student learning and development, ultimately promoting a more inclusive and effective educational experience for all students. As she said that:

"I regularly communicate with other professionals about student progress, successes, and areas needing additional support". (IDI-06)

Likewise, Art (pseudonym) she highlighted the importance of collaboration with other special education professionals for fostering positive interactions with students with special needs. By working together, educators can pool their expertise and resources to create a supportive and inclusive learning environment. Collaborative efforts allow for the sharing of strategies and insights to better meet the diverse needs of students with special education requirements. Through this interaction, professionals can enhance their understanding of effective practices and techniques, ultimately improving outcomes for students with special needs. This collaborative approach demonstrates a commitment to providing comprehensive support and ensuring the success of every student in the special education program. As she said that:

"I collaborate with other special education through the professionals' personnel for being have a good interaction to the students with special education". (IDI-01)

Flexibility and Adaptability

Flexibility and adaptability are essential qualities for educators to effectively respond to the diverse needs of students and changing circumstances in the classroom. Being flexible allows teachers to adjust instructional strategies, materials, and approaches based on individual student needs and learning styles. Moreover, adaptability enables educators to modify lesson plans and activities on the fly

to address unexpected challenges or capitalize on emerging opportunities for learning. Overall, the ability to be flexible and adaptable empowers teachers to create dynamic and inclusive learning environments that support the growth and success of all students.

According to Mr. Smile (pseudonym) he emphasizing the importance of establishing clear and measurable learning objectives that can be attained through various instructional approaches. By defining specific goals, educators provide clarity and direction for student learning. Additionally, by ensuring that these objectives are measurable, educators can effectively assess student progress and adjust instruction as needed. The emphasis on utilizing different instructional approaches acknowledges the diverse needs and learning styles of students, allowing for flexibility in how objectives are achieved. Overall, this approach promotes a comprehensive and adaptable teaching strategy that maximizes student learning outcomes.

"I focus on clear and measurable learning objectives that can be achieved through different instructional approaches". (IDI-02)

Furthermore, Chinita (pseudonym) she highlighted the ability to make real-time revisions and adjustments to their lesson plans when faced with challenges during instruction. By being responsive to the needs and dynamics of the classroom environment, educators can adapt their teaching strategies to better meet the needs of their students. This flexibility allows for immediate responses to unexpected issues or difficulties that may arise, ensuring that learning objectives are effectively addressed and student engagement is maintained. Overall, the willingness and capability to make on-the-spot revisions demonstrate the educator's commitment to providing quality instruction and maximizing learning opportunities for their students. As she said that:

"I can make on the spot revisions and adjustments in my lesson plan if there are challenges encountered with them during the lesson". (IDI-03)

Moreover, Sunflower (pseudonym) she emphasizing the importance of adaptability for new teachers when teaching students with special needs. It highlights the need to remain open to change and adjust teaching methods in response to challenges encountered in the classroom. By reviewing and revising lesson plans, educators can identify areas that require modification to better accommodate students' needs. Additionally, the inclusion of visual aids, manipulatives, and other support materials can enhance students' understanding and engagement. Moreover, the statement underscores the importance of being sensitive and understanding of students' needs and limitations when modifying classroom activities. By continuously considering and addressing these needs, educators can effectively support students' development and success in learning, fostering an inclusive and supportive learning environment. As she said that:

"Bilang bagong guro, mahalaga ang kakayahang umangkop sa mga plano at pamamaraan sa pagtuturo para sa mga mag-aaral na may espesyal na pangangailangan. Sa mga hamon na iyong na-encounter, maging bukas sa pagbabago. Suriin at repasuhin ang iyong mga lesson plans upang makita kung ano ang dapat baguhin. Maaaring kailanganin mong magdagdag ng visual aids, manipulatives, o iba pang materyales para mas madaling maunawaan ng mga mag-aaral ang mga aralin. Mahalaga ring maging sensitibo at maunawain sa kanilang mga pangangailangan. Sa pamamagitan ng pagtutok sa kanilang mga limitasyon at patuloy na pag-aadjust sa iyong pagtuturo, matutulungan mong mapalakas ang kanilang pag-unlad at tagumpay sa pag-aaral". (IDI-04)

(As a new teacher, it is important to be adaptable in your plans and teaching methods for students with special needs. When you encounter challenges, be open to change. Review and assess your lesson plans to identify what needs to be adjusted. You may need to add visual aids, manipulatives, or other materials to help students better understand the lessons. It is also essential to be sensitive and understanding of their needs. By focusing on their limitations and continually adjusting your teaching, you can help strengthen their growth and success in learning.)

Additionally, Mayumi (pseudonym) she highlighted the approaches use in lesson planning, which involves detailed preparation while maintaining flexibility to accommodate student needs during instruction. By creating thorough lesson plans, educators establish a framework for instruction that aligns with learning objectives and curriculum standards. However, the speaker also emphasizes the importance of adaptability, recognizing that student needs may vary and unexpected challenges may arise. Remaining flexible allows educators to make real-time adjustments to their lesson plans, such as modifying activities or pacing, to better meet the needs of their students and ensure optimal learning outcomes. This approach promotes responsiveness and student-centered teaching, fostering a supportive and dynamic learning environment. As she said that:

"I prepare detailed lesson plans but remain flexible to adjust them based on student needs during the lesson". (IDI-06)

Likewise, Art (pseudonym) she emphasizing the importance of lesson planning as a foundational tool in teaching, highlighting its role in providing structure and guidance for instruction. The speaker mentions using a weekly learning plan as a guide, which outlines targeted tasks, topics, and objectives for instruction. Moreover, in the Special Education Program, the Individual Educational Plan (IEP) plays a crucial role, as it documents the strengths and weaknesses of each learner and serves as a roadmap for personalized support. The IEP also serves as a record of students' progress and improvements over time, ensuring that instruction remains tailored to their evolving needs. Overall, these planning tools help educators in both general and special education settings to effectively organize and deliver instruction that meets the diverse needs of their students. As she said that:

"Lesson planning is one of our tools in teaching. In our field, I used the weekly learning plan as our guide in teaching, in which the targeted task and topic were indicated and the objectives as well. In the Special Education Program, it requires the Individual

Educational Plan (IEP) wherein the strengths and weaknesses of each learner was stated and this is where we record their improvements as well". (IDI-01)

Strong Motivation from One's Students

Strong motivation from one's students is a powerful catalyst for an educator's dedication and enthusiasm in teaching. When students demonstrate genuine interest, engagement, and enthusiasm for learning, it fosters a rewarding and fulfilling teaching experience. Witnessing students actively participate, strive for excellence, and achieve their goals can inspire educators to continually innovate, refine their teaching methods, and go above and beyond to support their students' growth and success. This mutual exchange of motivation creates a positive feedback loop, reinforcing the teacher-student relationship and contributing to a vibrant and dynamic learning environment.

According to Mr. Smile (pseudonym) he highlighted the intrinsic rewards that come from witnessing students with special needs learn, grow, and achieve their full potential. Observing their progress and accomplishments serves as a source of fulfillment and validation for educators, reaffirming the impact of their efforts and dedication. It underscores the importance of recognizing and celebrating the unique achievements of each student, regardless of their challenges or limitations. This rewarding experience not only motivates educators to continue their work but also reinforces the value of inclusive education and the potential for all students to thrive given the right support and opportunities. As he said that:

"Witnessing students with special needs learn, grow and achieve their full potential is already a rewarding experience". (IDI-02)

Furthermore, Mayumi (pseudonym) she reflects the meaningful relationships that educators develop with their students, emphasizing the special connections forged in the classroom. Witnessing students' growth in confidence and independence serves as a powerful source of motivation for the speaker, highlighting the impact of their support and guidance. These connections go beyond academic achievements, encompassing personal development and empowerment. The speaker's motivation is fueled by the transformative journey they embark on alongside their students, fostering a sense of pride and fulfillment in seeing them flourish. This highlights the profound influence educators have in shaping students' lives and underscores the intrinsic rewards of teaching. As she said that:

"The connections I form with my students are truly special. Seeing their growth in confidence and independence is incredibly motivating". (IDI-06)

Moreover, Mysterious (pseudonym) he encapsulates the satisfaction that comes from observing special needs students develop, learn, and achieve their full potential. Witnessing their progress and growth serves as a source of fulfillment and validation for the speaker, reaffirming the impact of their support and guidance. It underscores the transformative power of education in empowering students to overcome challenges and realize their capabilities. This satisfaction reflects the educator's commitment to fostering an inclusive and supportive learning environment where all students can thrive. Ultimately, it highlights the inherent rewards of making a positive difference in the lives of special needs students and contributing to their journey of success and achievement. As he said that:

"It's already satisfying to watch special needs students develop, learn, and reach their full potential". (IDI-07)

Additionally, Music (pseudonym) he highlighted the motivation to teach students with special needs, rooted in their passionate commitment to equipping them with the knowledge and skills necessary for independence in the future. Their desire to empower students to navigate life autonomously, without relying on external assistance, reflects a deep sense of responsibility and dedication to their well-being and success. This motivation is driven by a genuine belief in the importance of providing students with the tools they need to thrive and lead fulfilling lives; despite the challenges they may face. Ultimately, the speaker's passion for teaching students with special needs stems from a desire to make a tangible and lasting impact on their lives, enabling them to achieve self-sufficiency and realize their full potential.

"I motivated to teach students with special needs because I have a passion to give them knowledge in able the to survive things in a near future without the needs of help with another person". (IDI-13)

Likewise, Chatterbox (pseudonym) he emphasizing to finds inspiration and drive to continue teaching students with special needs in witnessing their progress and success. It brings them immense joy and fulfillment to observe the growth and development of their students as they learn. Being a part of their journey towards realizing their dreams and reaching their potential brings the speaker a profound sense of purpose in their role as a teacher. Additionally, the ability to positively impact the lives of others and contribute to their well-being serves as a significant motivation. Overall, the speaker's dedication to teaching students with special needs is fueled by the meaningful connections formed with their students and the fulfillment derived from supporting their growth and success. As he said that:

"Ang nagbibigay sa akin ng inspirasyon at nagtutulak sa akin na patuloy na magturo sa mga mag-aaral na may espesyal na pangangailangan ay ang kanilang pag-unlad at tagumpay. Nakakatuwa at nakakataba ng puso na makita ang kanilang pagbabago at pag-unlad habang sila ay natututo. Ang pagiging bahagi ng kanilang paglalakbay tungo sa pagkamit ng kanilang mga pangarap at potensyal ay nagbibigay sa akin ng kasiyahan at kahulugan sa aking trabaho bilang isang guro. Bukod pa rito, ang pakiramdam na nakakatulong at nakakapagbigay ng positibong epekto sa buhay ng iba ay isa ring malaking motibasyon para sa akin". (IDI-14)

(I inspire and drives me to continue teaching students with special needs is their progress and success. It is heartwarming and fulfilling to witness their growth and development as they learn. Being part of their journey towards achieving their dreams and potential brings me joy and purpose in my role as a teacher. Additionally, the feeling of being able to help and positively impact the lives of others is also a significant motivation for me.)

Research Question 3: What insights do novice teachers can share with regards to teaching students with special needs?

This question delved into the unique perspectives, observations, and understandings gained by novice teachers teaching students with special need. Novice teachers embarking on the journey of teaching students with special needs can share valuable insights based on their experiences. Firstly, they may emphasize the importance of flexibility and adaptability in their teaching approach, as every student's needs are unique and may require different strategies for support. Additionally, they might stress the significance of collaboration with special education professionals, colleagues, and families to gain insights and support tailored to each student's requirements. Novice teachers may also highlight the value of ongoing professional development to continuously refine their skills and stay abreast of best practices in inclusive education. Furthermore, they might emphasize the significance of patience, empathy, and resilience in navigating the challenges and successes of teaching students with special needs, as building meaningful relationships and fostering a supportive learning environment are fundamental to their success. Overall, novice teachers can share insights that underscore the holistic and dynamic nature of teaching students with special needs, emphasizing the importance of dedication, collaboration, and ongoing growth in meeting the diverse needs of every learner.

In the responses of the participants, there were four emerging themes that the researcher has found. The following themes were: The Value of Perseverance and Resilience, Establishing Positive Relationship with Students with Special Needs, Empathy and Compassion, Continuous Learning and Collaboration and Importance of Strong Parents Support.

Table 4. Insight of Novice teachers in teaching students with Special Needs

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
The Value of Perseverance and Resilience	<p>“Students with special needs really needs attention and understanding from the persons around them. They also need time to learn in their own pace and they almost considerations.” -IDI-03</p> <p>“As a novice teacher teaching students with special needs, I’ve learned a lot specially in adjusting my mood wings to them, I learned that I must have long patience to understand their difference and learned to love them just like as my own child. Because in this for concerns of my classroom my students need me, needs may care and needs me more.” -IDI-04</p> <p>“I truly believe that there is no "one size fits all" approach when it comes to education. Every individual has their own unique set of strengths, weaknesses, and learning styles. By tailoring lessons to meet each person's specific needs, we can unlock a world of learning possibilities.” -IDI-06</p> <p>“Everything happens for a reason. Patience will be merely test upon handling the Learners with Special Needs (LSeNs). Maybe it is small thing for us, but for them it’s a big achievement for them for an instance in buttoning and unbutton the clothes.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“I learned about being a teacher must be flexible on doing things because we need flexible to give our students a good knowledge.” -IDI-13</p>
Establishing Positive Relationship with Students with Special Needs	<p>“Building relationships is vital. Take time to understand each student's strengths, and preferred learning methods.” -IDI-02</p> <p>“Give them enough love, attention and understanding for them to be able to learn easily and love your subject. Talk to them about their life and challenges they face every day.” -IDI-03</p> <p>“To my fellow teachers who are teaching students with special needs, I want to express how proud I am of them. It's not easy to care for and teach these learners; you really have to dedicate time, effort, patience, and support to make them feel that they are not different from everyone else, to make them feel loved and valued. To my co-teachers teaching students with special needs, let's keep fighting for them because they need us.” IDI-04</p> <p>“As an educator, it's important to always be ready to adjust lesson plans at a moment's notice based on the unique needs of your students. Being able to adapt on the fly is a key skill that can help ensure each student receives the support they need to succeed. So, always keep an open mind and be flexible in your approach to teaching.” IDI-06</p>
Empathy and Compassion	<p>“Well in the Special Education Program teacher has the passion, perseverance, a lot of patience and full of love and understanding.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“Breaking down complex tasks into manageable steps to make learning less overwhelming is what I've seen affective.” -IDI-02</p> <p>“Give easier tasks, clear and direct instruction, given sample time for them to learn.” (IDI-03)</p> <p>“In teaching, our strategies depend on the learners’ capabilities. I use different strategies for each of them because they have varying needs. What I do is I practice our daily routines with them from the start until we end, so they can adapt and also develop discipline, even though sometimes adjustments are needed for them.” -IDI-04</p> <p>“I have found that using visual schedules and clear instructions helps me create a predictable environment that fosters a sense of security.” (IDI-06)</p> <p>Know first their strengths and weaknesses, their history so that the teacher will know what do the skills that a child will be develop. Let the student feel that we as teacher whom they can be trusted.” -IDI-01</p>
Continuous Learning	<p>“I seek guidance from experienced special education teachers. I was also able to attend seminar during my 1st</p>

and Collaboration	<p>year in teaching about handling students with special needs.” -IDI-02</p> <p>“More patience and understanding to students with special needs.” -IDI-03</p> <p>“Of course, to my co-teachers we will not forget to attend seminars, workshops, training to handle out students it's not about us it's about the journey and life of our student's so it's better that we do research and be critical or how we get the students learners in teaching them every day.” -IDI-04</p> <p>“Connecting with other teachers to share successful strategies and learning materials can be a big help.” -IDI-06</p>
Importance of Strong Parents Support	<p>“More training and seminars. Mentoring and seek help to the experts.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“Parents and teachers must go hand-in-hand and to achieve child's success. We must work together to create a nurturing and stimulating learning environment.” -IDI-02</p> <p>“Give your child the love, attention, and understanding they want give the time to talk and share their thoughts.” -IDI-03</p> <p>“To those parents who have children with special needs, do not lose hope in caring for your children because of their special needs. We, as parents, serve as their inspiration to live happily. Your love, care, patience, and understanding are significant aids for your children. Do not worry because as a teacher, we do our best so that they can experience the life they desire in this world as they grow up.” -IDI-04</p> <p>“Your child has the potential to achieve great things with the right support system. Remember, you're not alone on this journey.” -IDI-06</p> <p>“Parents of special needs children should be encouraged to spend as much time as possible with their children because of their unique needs. This will help the children grow up to be resilient and appreciative of your love, care, understanding, and patience. In my experience as a teacher, the best thing I can do for my students is to help them realize their dreams and live their lives to the fullest.” IDI-14</p>

The Value of Perseverance and Resilience

The Value of Perseverance and resilience are essential qualities that enable individuals to overcome obstacles and achieve success despite challenges. They embody the determination to persist in the face of adversity, demonstrating resilience in bouncing back from setbacks. These qualities empower individuals to navigate difficulties, learn from failures, and continue striving towards their goals. Moreover, perseverance and resilience foster a positive mindset and a sense of optimism, driving individuals to persevere even in the most challenging circumstances. Ultimately, they serve as powerful catalysts for personal growth, resilience, and achievement, enabling individuals to overcome obstacles and thrive in both their personal and professional endeavors.

According to Chinita (pseudonym) she emphasizing the importance of providing attention and understanding to students with special needs, highlighting their unique learning requirements. The speaker underscores the necessity of allowing these students to learn at their own pace, emphasizing the need for patience and flexibility in teaching approaches. Additionally, the mention of "considerations" suggests a need for accommodations and adjustments to support their learning journey effectively. Overall, the speaker emphasizes the significance of creating a supportive and inclusive environment that acknowledges and meets the individual needs of students with special needs, fostering their development and success. As she said that:

"Students with special needs really needs attention and understanding from the persons around them. They also need time to learn in their own pace and they almost considerations". (IDI-03)

Furthermore, Sunflower (pseudonym) she shares insights gained from teaching students with special needs. They acknowledge the importance of adapting their approach and mindset to effectively connect with their students. The mention of adjusting "mood swings" suggests a willingness to be flexible and empathetic to meet the diverse emotional needs of their students. The recognition of the necessity for patience underscores the challenges inherent in understanding and addressing the differences among students with special needs. Furthermore, the analogy of loving students like their own child highlights the deep emotional investment and sense of responsibility the teacher feels towards their students' well-being and success. Overall, this reflection illustrates the transformative journey of growth and learning experienced by the novice teacher as they navigate the complexities of teaching students with special needs. As she said that:

“As a novice teacher teaching students with special needs, I've learned a lot specially in adjusting my mood wings to them, I learned that I must have long patience to understand their difference and learned to love them just like as my own child. Because in this for concerns of my classroom my students need me, needs may care and needs me more”. (IDI-04)

Moreover, Mayumi (pseudonym) she belief in the importance of individualized education and the recognition that each student is unique. They emphasize that a standardized approach to education is inadequate because of the diversity in strengths, weaknesses, and learning styles among individuals. Instead, the speaker advocates for tailoring lessons to accommodate the specific needs of each student. By doing so, they believe that educators can unlock a wealth of learning opportunities for their students, allowing them to flourish and reach their full potential. This approach reflects a commitment to inclusive and personalized education, aiming to address the diverse needs of all learners. As she said that:

“I truly believe that there is no "one size fits all" approach when it comes to education. Every individual has their own unique set of strengths, weaknesses, and learning styles. By tailoring lessons to meet each person's specific needs, we can unlock a world of learning

possibilities". (IDI-06)

Additionally, Art (pseudonym) she reflects on the notion that everything occurs for a purpose and emphasizes the importance of patience when working with Learners with Special Needs (LSeNs). They suggest that what may seem insignificant to others can be a significant achievement for LSeNs, such as mastering simple tasks like buttoning and unbuttoning clothes. This perspective highlights the unique challenges and milestones faced by individuals with special needs, underscoring the significance of recognizing and celebrating even the smallest accomplishments. Overall, the statement conveys the speaker's understanding of the value of patience and the importance of acknowledging the achievements, no matter how small, of LSeNs in their learning journey. As she said that:

"Everything happens for a reason. Patience will be merely test upon handling the Learners with Special Needs (LSeNs). Maybe it is small thing for us, but for them it's a big achievement for them for an instance in buttoning and unbutton the clothes". (IDI-01)

Likewise, Music (pseudonym) he shares a key lesson learned about the necessity for flexibility in teaching. They acknowledge that as a teacher, being adaptable is crucial to effectively imparting knowledge to students. This recognition underscores the importance of adjusting teaching methods, approaches, and strategies to meet the diverse needs of students. The speaker emphasizes the role of flexibility in ensuring that students receive quality education tailored to their individual learning styles and preferences. Overall, this reflection highlights the value of adaptability in providing students with a robust and enriching learning experience. As he said that:

"I learned about being a teacher must be flexible on doing things because we need flexible to give our students a good knowledge". (IDI-13)

Establishing Positive Relationship with Students with Special Needs

Establishing positive relationships with students with special needs is essential for their overall well-being and academic success. It begins with showing genuine care, empathy, and understanding towards each student, acknowledging their unique strengths and challenges. Building trust through consistent support and encouragement fosters a sense of safety and belonging in the classroom. Effective communication and active listening are crucial for understanding students' individual needs and preferences. By creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment, educators can empower students with special needs to thrive and reach their full potential.

According to Mr. Smile (pseudonym) he emphasizing the importance of building relationships with students is underscored as a vital aspect of effective teaching. The speaker emphasizes the significance of investing time to understand each student individually, including their strengths and preferred learning methods. By doing so, educators can establish a rapport with their students, creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment. This approach fosters a deeper connection between teacher and student, which enhances engagement, motivation, and ultimately, academic success. Overall, the statement highlights the pivotal role of relationship-building in tailoring instruction to meet the unique needs of each student. As she said that: emphasizes the importance of providing students with special needs with love, attention, and understanding to facilitate their learning process and foster a positive attitude towards the subject. By building a supportive and caring relationship with students, educators create a conducive environment where students feel valued and supported. Additionally, the speaker advocates for engaging students in conversations about their lives and the challenges they encounter daily, allowing educators to gain insights into their experiences and tailor instruction accordingly. This approach promotes empathy, enhances rapport, and encourages a deeper connection between educators and students, ultimately contributing to a more meaningful and effective learning experience. As she said that:

"Building relationships is vital. Take time to understand each student's strengths, and preferred learning methods". (IDI-02)

Furthermore, Chinita (pseudonym) she emphasizing the importance of providing students with special needs with love, attention, and understanding to facilitate their learning process and foster a positive attitude towards the subject. By building a supportive and caring relationship with students, educators create a conducive environment where students feel valued and supported. Additionally, the speaker advocates for engaging students in conversations about their lives and the challenges they encounter daily, allowing educators to gain insights into their experiences and tailor instruction accordingly. This approach promotes empathy, enhances rapport, and encourages a deeper connection between educators and students, ultimately contributing to a more meaningful and effective learning experience. As she said that:

"Give them enough love, attention and understanding for them to be able to learn easily and love your subject. Talk to them about their life and challenges they face every day". (IDI-03)

Moreover, Sunflower (pseudonym) she expresses admiration and appreciation for fellow teachers who teach students with special needs. They acknowledge the challenges involved in caring for and educating these learners, highlighting the necessity of dedicating time, effort, patience, and support to ensure their well-being and success. The speaker emphasizes the importance of making students feel included, loved, and valued, despite their differences. They rally their co-teachers to continue advocating for students with special needs, underscoring the significance of their role in providing essential support and guidance. Overall, the message conveys a sense of solidarity and determination among teachers to champion the rights and needs of students with special needs. As she said that:

"To the other teachers teaching students with special needs, I just want to tell them that I 'am proud of them kasi hindi madali mag

alaga magturo ng mga ganitong learners maglalaan ka talaga ng time, effort, patience and support para ma feel din nila na hindi sila kakaiba sa lahat, para ma feels nila na kamahal mahal sila. To my co-teachers teaching with special needs laban lng po tayo para sa kanila kasi they need us". (IDI-04)

(To my fellow teachers who are teaching students with special needs, I want to express how proud I am of them. It's not easy to care for and teach these learners; you really have to dedicate time, effort, patience, and support to make them feel that they are not different from everyone else, to make them feel loved and valued. To my co-teachers teaching students with special needs, let's keep fighting for them because they need us.)

Additionally, Mayumi (pseudonym) she highlighted the necessity for educators to be flexible and responsive to the individual needs of their students. They emphasize the importance of being prepared to modify lesson plans quickly to provide tailored support. The ability to adapt on the fly is deemed essential for ensuring each student receives the necessary assistance to thrive academically. Furthermore, the speaker advocates for educators to maintain an open-minded approach and be willing to adjust their teaching methods as needed. Overall, the message underscores the significance of adaptability and flexibility in promoting effective teaching practices and meeting the diverse needs of students. As she said that:

"As an educator, it's important to always be ready to adjust lesson plans at a moment's notice based on the unique needs of your students. Being able to adapt on the fly is a key skill that can help ensure each student receives the support they need to succeed. So, always keep an open mind and be flexible in your approach to teaching". (IDI-06)

Likewise, Art (pseudonym) she highlighted the essential qualities of teachers in the Special Education Program. They emphasize that educators in this field possess qualities such as passion, perseverance, patience, love, and understanding. These characteristics are vital for effectively supporting students with diverse learning needs and challenges. Passion drives educators to make a meaningful impact, while perseverance enables them to overcome obstacles and continue striving for their students' success. Patience is crucial in navigating the unique complexities of teaching students with special needs, while love and understanding foster a supportive and nurturing learning environment. Overall, these qualities are fundamental for educators in the Special Education Program to create positive and inclusive educational experiences for their students. As she said that:

"Well in the Special Education Program teacher has the passion, perseverance, a lot of patience and full of love and understanding". (IDI-01)

Empathy and Compassion

Empathy is the ability to understand and share the feelings of others, enabling individuals to connect emotionally and offer support and understanding. It involves recognizing and validating someone else's experiences, fostering a sense of solidarity and compassion. Compassion, on the other hand, goes beyond empathy and involves taking action to alleviate suffering or distress. It prompts individuals to respond with kindness, empathy, and a desire to help others in need. Together, empathy and compassion form the basis of meaningful relationships and promote a sense of caring and connection within communities.

According to Mr. Smile (pseudonym) he highlighted the effectiveness of breaking down complex tasks into smaller, more manageable steps to facilitate learning. By doing so, they aim to reduce feelings of overwhelm and improve comprehension. This approach allows learners to focus on one aspect of a task at a time, making it easier to grasp and apply concepts gradually. The speaker suggests that this method has proven to be effective in their experience, indicating its practical utility in educational settings. Overall, the statement underscores the importance of employing strategies that cater to individual learning needs and promote a deeper understanding of complex topics. As he said that:

"Breaking down complex tasks into manageable steps to make learning less overwhelming is what I've seen affective". (IDI-02)

Furthermore, Chinita (pseudonym) she advocates for providing students with special needs with easier tasks, clear and direct instructions, and ample time to learn. By offering simpler tasks, educators can help students build confidence and gradually progress in their learning journey. Clear and direct instructions aid in minimizing confusion and ensuring that students understand what is expected of them. Additionally, allowing sufficient time for learning enables students to absorb information at their own pace and reinforces their understanding of concepts. Overall, these strategies are aimed at supporting the diverse learning needs of students with special needs, fostering a conducive environment for their academic growth and success. As she said that:

"Give easier tasks, clear and direct instruction, given sample time for them to learn". (IDI-03)

Moreover, Sunflower (pseudonym) she emphasizing the importance of tailoring teaching strategies to the individual capabilities and needs of learners. They recognize the diverse requirements of each student and adapt their approach accordingly. By incorporating different strategies based on these varying needs, the speaker aims to create an inclusive learning environment where every student can thrive. The speaker also highlights the significance of daily routines in promoting adaptation and discipline among learners, acknowledging the occasional need for adjustments to accommodate their needs. Overall, the statement reflects a commitment to personalized and responsive teaching practices, ensuring that each student receives the support necessary for their development and success. As she said that:

“In teaching, our strategies depend on the learners’ capabilities. I use different strategies for each of them because they have varying needs. What I do is I practice our daily routines with them from the start until we end, so they can adapt and also develop discipline, even though sometimes adjustments are needed for them”. (IDI-04)

Additionally, Mayumi (pseudonym) she discusses their experience of utilizing visual schedules and clear instructions in their teaching approach. They note that these tools help establish a predictable environment, which in turn cultivates a sense of security among their students. By providing visual schedules, the speaker offers a tangible framework for students to follow, aiding in comprehension and organization. Clear instructions further enhance understanding and reduce ambiguity, contributing to a structured and supportive learning atmosphere. Overall, the speaker's emphasis on predictability and security underscores their commitment to creating an environment conducive to their students' well-being and learning. As she said that:

“I've found that using visual schedules and clear instructions helps me create a predictable environment that fosters a sense of security”. (IDI-06)

Likewise, Art (pseudonym) she emphasizing the importance of understanding students' strengths, weaknesses, and personal history to inform teaching strategies effectively. By gaining insights into each student's background and abilities, educators can tailor instruction to address their specific needs and promote skill development. Additionally, the speaker highlights the significance of building trust between teachers and students, creating a supportive and nurturing learning environment. When students feel trusted and valued by their teachers, they are more likely to engage actively in the learning process and feel empowered to reach their full potential. Overall, the statement underscores the value of individualized support and fostering positive teacher-student relationships in promoting student success. As she said that:

“Know first their strengths and weaknesses, their history so that the teacher will know what do the skills that a child will be develop. Let the student feel that we as teacher whom they can be trusted”. (IDI-01)

Continuous Learning and Collaboration

Continuous learning involves the ongoing acquisition of knowledge, skills, and insights to enhance professional practice. It enables educators to stay updated on best practices, research findings, and innovative teaching methodologies, fostering their growth and effectiveness in the classroom. Collaboration, on the other hand, entails working collectively with colleagues, stakeholders, and community partners to share expertise, resources, and ideas. By collaborating with others, educators can leverage collective wisdom, address challenges collaboratively, and cultivate a supportive learning environment. Together, continuous learning and collaboration empower educators to adapt to changing educational landscapes, optimize student learning experiences, and drive positive outcomes in education.

According to Mr. Smile (pseudonym) he highlighted their proactive approach to seeking guidance and professional development in the field of special education. By consulting experienced special education teachers, the speaker demonstrates a willingness to learn from those with expertise and practical knowledge. Additionally,

attending seminars focused on handling students with special needs during their first year of teaching indicates a commitment to acquiring specialized skills and knowledge relevant to their role. Overall, the speaker's initiative in seeking guidance and professional development opportunities underscores their dedication to effectively supporting students with special needs and continuously improving their practice as an educator. As he said that:

“I seek guidance from experienced special education teachers. I was also able to attend seminar during my 1st year in teaching about handling students with special needs”. (IDI-02)

Furthermore, (pseudonym) she highlighted the importance of exercising patience and understanding when working with students with special needs. By demonstrating patience, educators create a supportive and inclusive learning environment where students feel valued and accepted. Understanding the unique challenges and abilities of each student allows teachers to tailor their approach to meet individual needs effectively. Patience and understanding foster trust and rapport between educators and students, empowering the latter to engage actively in their learning journey. Overall, prioritizing patience and understanding promotes positive learning experiences and enhances the overall well-being and success of students with special needs. As she said that:

“More patience and understanding to students with special needs”. (IDI-03)

Moreover, (pseudonym) she emphasizing the importance of continuous professional development for teachers in order to effectively support their students. Attending seminars, workshops, and training sessions enables educators to stay informed about best practices and innovative strategies in teaching. By engaging in research and critical thinking, teachers can refine their approaches to meet the diverse needs of their students. The speaker highlights the collective responsibility of educators to prioritize the educational journey and well-being of their students above all else. Overall, the statement underscores the commitment of teachers to ongoing growth and improvement in order to provide the best possible education for their students. As she said that:

“Of course, to my co-teachers we will not forget to attend seminars, workshops, training to handle out students it's not about us it's about the journey and life of our student's so it's better that we do research and be critical or how we get the students learners in teaching

them every day”. (IDI-04)

Additionally, Mayumi (pseudonym) she emphasizing the value of collaboration among teachers as a means of improving teaching practices and supporting student learning. By connecting with other educators, teachers can share successful strategies and learning materials, benefiting from each other's expertise and experiences. Collaboration allows teachers to access a wider range of resources and ideas, enabling them to address challenges more effectively and enhance the quality of instruction. Overall, the statement highlights the importance of professional networking and knowledge sharing in promoting continuous improvement in education. As she said that:

"Connecting with other teachers to share successful strategies and learning materials can be a big help". (IDI-06)

Likewise, Art (pseudonym) she emphasizing the significance of ongoing professional development opportunities, such as training sessions and seminars, for educators. By participating in these activities, teachers can enhance their skills, expand their knowledge base, and stay abreast of emerging trends and best practices in education. Additionally, the speaker emphasizes the importance of seeking mentorship from experienced colleagues and consulting experts in the field. These mentorship relationships and consultations enable teachers to receive guidance, support, and valuable insights to improve their teaching effectiveness and better meet the needs of their students. Overall, the statement highlights the proactive approach of educators in continuously seeking opportunities for growth and improvement in their profession. As she said that:

"More training and seminars. Mentoring and seek help to the experts". (IDI-01)

Importance of Strong Parents Support

Strong parental support plays a crucial role in a child's educational journey and overall development. When parents actively engage in their child's education, it fosters a positive home environment that reinforces learning and academic success. By showing interest in their child's schooling, providing encouragement, and advocating for their needs, parents demonstrate the value of education and instill a sense of importance in their child. Additionally, strong parental involvement facilitates communication between home and school, allowing educators to better understand a child's strengths, weaknesses, and individual needs, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of teaching strategies and interventions. Overall, strong parental support is instrumental in nurturing a child's academic progress, social-emotional well-being, and lifelong learning habits.

According to Mr. Smile (pseudonym) he emphasizing the importance of collaboration between parents and teachers in supporting a child's success in education. By working hand-in-hand, parents and teachers can create a cohesive partnership that enhances the learning experience for the child. Collaboration allows for the alignment of goals, strategies, and support systems both at home and in the classroom. Additionally, by fostering open communication and mutual respect, parents and teachers can ensure consistency in expectations and reinforcement of learning. Overall, the statement underscores the collective responsibility of both parents and teachers in creating a nurturing and stimulating learning environment that promotes the holistic development of the child. As he said that:

"Parents and teachers must go hand-in-hand and to achieve child's success. We must work together to create a nurturing and stimulating learning environment". (IDI-02)

Furthermore, Chinita (pseudonym) she emphasizing the importance of providing love, attention, and understanding to children, highlighting the significance of communication and emotional support. By giving children, the love and attention they need, parents and caregivers create a nurturing environment where children feel valued and supported. Additionally, by taking the time to talk and share thoughts with children, adults demonstrate an openness to listening and understanding their perspectives. This fosters healthy communication patterns and strengthens the bond between adults and children. Overall, the statement underscores the importance of positive interactions and emotional connections in promoting the well-being and development of children. As she said that:

"Give your child the love, attention, and understanding they want give the time to talk and share their thoughts". (IDI-03)

Moreover, Sunflower (pseudonym) she addresses parents of children with special needs, offering words of encouragement and support. They acknowledge the challenges parents may face but urge them not to lose hope in caring for their children. The speaker emphasizes the crucial role parents play as sources of inspiration for their children's happiness and well-being. They highlight the importance of love, care, patience, and understanding in supporting children with special needs. Additionally, the speaker reassures parents that teachers are dedicated to providing the best possible support to help their children lead fulfilling lives. Overall, the message conveys empathy, understanding, and solidarity with parents navigating the complexities of raising children with special needs. As she said that:

"To those parents who have children with special needs, do not lose hope in caring for your children because of their special needs. We, as parents, serve as their inspiration to live happily. Your love, care, patience, and understanding are significant aids for your children. Do not worry because as a teacher, we do our best so that they can experience the life they desire in this world as they grow up". (IDI-04)

Additionally, Mayumi (pseudonym) she offers encouragement and reassurance to parents, affirming their child's potential for success with the appropriate support system. By acknowledging the challenges parents may face, the speaker seeks to alleviate feelings of

isolation and provide comfort. They emphasize the importance of a supportive network, reminding parents that they are not alone in navigating the journey of raising a child. This message aims to instill hope and confidence in parents, highlighting the collective effort involved in nurturing their child's growth and development. Overall, the statement conveys empathy and support, encouraging parents to remain steadfast in their commitment to their child's well-being and future. As she said that:

“Your child has the potential to achieve great things with the right support system. Remember, you’re not alone on this journey”. (IDI-06)

Likewise, Chatterbox (pseudonym) she emphasizing the importance of parental involvement in the upbringing of special needs children, emphasizing the unique needs they require. The speaker suggests that spending ample time with their children can foster resilience and gratitude towards the love, care, understanding, and patience provided by their parents. Drawing from their experience as a teacher, the speaker highlights their role in facilitating students' realization of their aspirations and enabling them to lead fulfilling lives. Overall, the statement underscores the collaborative effort between parents and teachers in nurturing special needs children to achieve their potential and lead meaningful lives. As she said that:

“Parents of special needs children should be encouraged to spend as much time as possible with their children because of their unique needs. This will help the children grow up to be resilient and appreciative of your love, care, understanding, and patience. In my experience as a teacher, the best thing I can do for my students is to help them realize their dreams and live their lives to the fullest”. (IDI-14)

Conclusions

In conclusion, the study revealed that the participants had a variety of experiences, such as dealing with challenges in interaction with students with special needs, implementing teaching strategies to meet the needs of students, effectiveness in adapting teaching, and using diverse instructional materials. Additionally, the participants employed various coping mechanisms, such as individualized support and differentiation, building rapport and relationships, collaboration and professional development, flexibility and adaptability and strong motivation from one’s students. Furthermore, the participants shared valuable insights regarding the study, such as the value of perseverance and resilience, establishing positive relationship with students with special needs, empathy and compassion, continuous learning and collaboration and importance of strong parents’ support.

The findings of this study show that the novice teachers observed significant improvements in they’re their teaching effectiveness, job satisfaction, and overall well-being. Through tailored induction programs, ongoing professional development, and mentorship initiatives, these teachers reported feeling more confident in their roles and better equipped to address the unique challenges of teaching students with special needs.

In addition, the phenomenological exploration of novice teachers' experiences in inclusive education settings reveals profound insights into their challenges and triumphs. Novice teachers grapple with adapting teaching methods to meet diverse student needs, managing complex classroom dynamics, and navigating the emotional terrain of inclusive classrooms. Despite these challenges, the study illuminates’ opportunities for growth and development among novice teachers, highlighting the transformative potential of inclusive education experiences. Moving forward, it is essential to prioritize targeted support and professional development initiatives tailored to the unique needs of novice teachers in inclusive settings. By fostering a culture of collaboration, providing ongoing mentorship, and advocating for inclusive policies and resources, educational institutions can enhance inclusive practices and better support novice teachers on their journey towards becoming effective educators.

While this study sheds light on the subjective experiences of novice teachers, further research is needed to explore specific aspects of inclusive education and investigate the long-term impact of support mechanisms for novice teachers. Ultimately, by embracing the insights gleaned from this phenomenological exploration, educators and policymakers can work towards creating more inclusive and supportive learning environments for all students. I have encountered numerous challenges throughout my research journey, but one that particularly stands out my mind is the lack of funding or budget for my research. This issue is compounded by the fact I don’t have my own vehicle to go where the location of my participants and also some of them will busy that’s why we need to re-schedule of interview.

Furthermore, during the course of conducting my research, managing the availability of my participants’ time proved to be another challenge. There were instances when the agreed-upon interview time had to be extended due to their busy schedules. Consequently, it took a considerate among of time to complete the interviewing process.

Indeed, the researcher has taken the risk, and as a result of accepting this challenge, the final product of her best effort was accomplished for her personal dedication. The researcher was hoping that this study would be leave a mask on those who read it and consider it a piece of work worthy of credence.

References

Adams, D., Harris, A., & Jones, M. S. (2018). Teacher-parent collaboration for an inclusive classroom: Success for every child. *MOJES: Malaysian Online Journal of Educational Sciences*, 4(3), 58-72. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1106456.pdf>

- Alber., J. David., C. & Vizmanos., J. (2019). Pressures on public school teacher and Implications on quality; Philippine Institute for Development Studies.
- Anderson, S. E., & Putman, R. S. (2020). Special education teachers' experience, confidence, beliefs, and knowledge about integrating technology. *Journal of Special Education Technology*, 35(1), 37-50. <https://doi.org/10.1177/016264341983640>
- Armstrong, T. (2018) Multiple intelligences in the classroom. Washington DC: Association of School Curriculum Development.
- Bandura, A. (1997). Self-efficacy and health behaviour. *Cambridge handbook of psychology, health and medicine*, 160-162 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/9781119057840.ch111>.
- Baumeister, R. F., & Leary, M. R. (2019). The need to belong: Desire for interpersonal attachments as a fundamental human motivation. *Psychological Bulletin*, 117(3), 497-529.
- Bhandari, P. (2023). Qualitative Research: Definition, Types, and Examples. *Research Methodology*. Retrieved from <https://www.research-methodology.net>
- Bloom, B., & Crabtree, B. F. (2006). The qualitative research interview. *Medical education*, 40(4), 314-321.
- Bradshaw, L. K., & Hammond, J. (2018). "The Impact of Instructional Materials on Student Learning: A Review of the Literature.
- Bricki, N. and Green, J. (2007) A Guide to Using Qualitative Research Methodology. <https://fieldresearch.msf.org/handle/10144/84230>.
- Brown, A., Smith, J., & Johnson, R. (2018). *Inclusive Education Practices: A Comprehensive Guide*. London: Academic Press.
- Brownell, M. T., Jones, N. D., Sohn, H., & Stark, K. (2020). Improving teaching quality for students with disabilities: Establishing a warrant for teacher education practice. *Teacher Education and Special Education*, 43(1), 28-44. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0888406419880351>
- Brown, C., Smith, J., & Wilson, R. (2018). *The Principles of Inclusive Education: Promoting Social Integration and Equal Opportunities in Schools*. *Educational Review*, 30(2), 140-157.
- Boyatzis, 1998; Mack et al., (2005). Exploring Behavioral Biases among Indian Investor: A Qualitative study: Jain Univeristy Bangalore, India 1-21 DOI: 10.20472/IAC.2019.045.024.
- Byrd, D. R., & Alexander, M. (2020). Investigating special education teachers' knowledge and skills: Preparing general teacher preparation for professional development. *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, 4(2), 72-82. <https://doi.org/10.33902/JPR.2020059790>
- Carcary, M. (2009). The research audit trail: A reflection on the role of an audit trail in qualitative research. *Electronic Journal of Business Research Methods*, 7(1), 1-10.
- Civitillo, S., Juang, L. P., & Schachner, M. K. (2018). Challenging Beliefs about Cultural Diversity in Education: A Synthesis and Critical Review of Trainings with Pre Service Teachers *Educational Research Review*, 24, 67-83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2018.01.003>
- Civitillo, S., Juang, L. P., & Schachner, M. K. (2018). Challenging Beliefs about Cultural Diversity in Education: A Synthesis and Critical Review of Trainings with Novice Teachers. *Educational Research Review*, 24, 67-83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2018.01.003>
- Chiwandire, T., Mwale, M., & Hlongwane, N. (2019). Funding and inclusion in higher education institutions for students with special needs. *Journal of Inclusive Education and Disability Studies*, 47(1), 34-49.
- Creswell, J. W. & Miller, D. L. (2000). Determining Validity in Qualitative Inquiry. *Theory Into Practice*, 39(3), 124-130. https://people.ucsc.edu/~ktellez/Creswell_validity2000.pdf
- Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (3rd ed.). Sage Publications.
- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research* (4th ed.). Boston, MA: Pearson. [https://www.scirp.org/\(S\(351jmbntvnst1aadkpozje\)\)/reference/ReferencesPa pers.aspx?ReferenceID=757162](https://www.scirp.org/(S(351jmbntvnst1aadkpozje))/reference/ReferencesPa pers.aspx?ReferenceID=757162)
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative inquiry & research design: Choosing among five approaches* (3rd ed.). Los Angeles Sage. <http://www.ceil-conicet.gov.ar/wpcontent/uploads/2018/04/CRESWELLQualitative-Inquiry-and-ResearchDesign-Creswell.pdf>
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *A concise introduction to mixed methods research*. SAGE publications.
- Creswell, J. W. (1998). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five traditions*. Sage Publications, Inc.
- Crispel, O., & Kasperski, R. (2021). The impact of teacher training in special education on the implementation of inclusion in mainstream classrooms. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 25(9), 1079-1090.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2019.1600590>

Cormier, C. J. (2023). It's not easy being green: Addressing Overrepresentation in special education through culturally responsive pedagogy. *Kappa Delta Pi Record*, 58(sup1), 10-15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00228958.2022.2132326>

Cornelius, K. E., Rosenberg, M. S., & Sandmel, K. N. (2020). Examining the impact of professional development and coaching on mentoring of novice special educators. *Action in Teacher Education*, 42(3), 253-270. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01626620.2019.1638847>

Cooc, N. (2019). Teaching students with special needs: International trends in school capacity and the need for teacher professional development. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 83, 27-41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2019.03.021>

Darling-Hammond, L., & Bransford, J. (2005). Preparing teachers for a changing world: What teachers need to know and be able to do. *Jossey-Bass. Educational Leadership*, 66(5), 46-53.

Darling-Hammond, L., & Richardson, N. (2019). The significance of continuous learning and collaboration in teaching students with special needs. *Journal of Educational Leadership*, 76(2), 58-72.

Davis, R. (2018). Empathy and compassion in teaching students with special needs. *Journal of Special Education*, 45(3), 125-135.

Deci, E., & Ryan, R. (2018). Self-determination theory: A consideration of human motivation universals. *The Cambridge handbook of personality psychology* (pp. 441-456).

Deci, E. L., & Kuhl, J. (1997). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American Psychologist*, 55(1), 68-78.

Dela Fuente, J. A. (2021). Implementing inclusive education in the Philippines: College teacher experiences with deaf students. *Issues in Educational Research*, 31(1), 94-110. <https://search.informit.org/doi/10.3316/informit.748877765999107>

Durlak, J. A., Weissberg, R. P., Dymnicki, A. B., Taylor, R. D., & Schellinger, K. B. (2020). The impact of enhancing students' social and emotional learning: A meta-analysis of school-based universal interventions. *Child development*, 82(1), 405-432.

Eccles, J. S., & Wigfield, A. (2018). Motivational beliefs, values, and goals. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 53(1), 109-132.

Fernandes, P. R. D. S., Jardim, J., & Lopes, M. C. D. S. (2021). The soft skills of special education teachers: Evidence from the literature. *Education Sciences*, 11(3), 125. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11030125>

Florian, L. (2006). The inclusive school: A synthesis of research evidence. *Research Papers in Education*, 21(3), 249-261.

Frederick, J. K., Raabe, G. R., Rogers, V. R., & Pizzica, J. (2020). Advocacy, collaboration, and intervention: A model of distance special education support services amid COVID-19. *Behavior analysis in practice*, 13(4), 748-756. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40617-020-00476-1>

Geiger W. L., Mickelson A., McKeown D., Barton J., Kleinhammer-Tramill J., Steinbrecher T. (2018). In America for special education teachers. In *Handbook of research on special education teacher preparation* (pp. 30-46).

Glaserfeld, E., (1989). Cognition, construction of knowledge, and teaching. *Synthese*, 80(1), 121-140.

Hattie, J., Fisher, D., & Frey, N. (2020). *Visible Learning for Literacy: Implementing the Practices That Work Best to Accelerate Student Learning*. Corwin.

Hazmi, A. N. A., & Ahmad, A. C. (2018). Universal Design for Learning to Support Access to the General Education Curriculum for Students with Intellectual Special educational needs. *World Journal of Education*, 8(2), 66. <https://doi.org/10.5430/wje.v8n2p66>

Heaton, J. (2021, September 30). “*Pseudonyms Are Used Throughout”: A Footnote, Unpacked. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 28(1), 123-132. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10778004211048379>

Heiskanen, N., Alasuutari, M., & Vehkakoski, T. (2019). Recording support measures in the sequential pedagogical documents of children with special education needs. *Journal of early intervention*, 41(4), 321-339. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1053815119854997>

Hong, S., & Kim, H. (2018). Novice teachers' self-efficacy in inclusive education: What are the contributing factors? *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 74, 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2018.04.005>

Hsieh, H. F., & Shannon, S. E. (2005). Three approaches to qualitative content analysis. *Qualitative health research*, 15(9), 1277-1288.

Hwang, A., & Roth, D. A. (2020). "Effects of teacher autonomy support and student autonomous motivation on learning in physical education". *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, 82(2), 217-225.

Jones, R., & Bender, W. (2022). The role of parental support in teaching students with special needs. *Journal of Special Education and Family Engagement*, 58(4), 112-128.

- Kispal, A. (2018). *The Impact of Instructional Materials on Student Learning: A Review of the Literature*. Education Development Trust.
- Klein, H.K., & Myers M.D (1999). A set of principles for conducting and evaluating interpretive field studies in information systems. *MIS Quarterly* (23)1, 67-93.
- Koenen, A. K., Vervoort, E., Verschueren, K., & Spilt, J. L. (2019). Teacher–student relationships in special education: The value of the Teacher Relationship Interview. *Journal of Psychoeducational Assessment*, 37(7), 874-886. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734282918803033>
- Kolb, D. A. (1984). *Experiential Learning: Experience as the Source of Learning and Development*. Prentice Hall.
- Korstjens, I., & Moser, A. (2018). Series: Practical guidance to qualitative research. Part 4: Trustworthiness and publishing. *European Journal of General Practice*, 24(1), 120-124.
- Kraayenoord, C.E., Moni, K., Jobling, A., Elkins, J., Koppenhaver, D., & Miller, R. (2019). The writing achievement, metacognitive knowledge of writing and motivation of middle school students with learning difficulties.
- Kraft, M. A., Blazar, D., & Hogan, D. (2018). "The effect of teacher coaching on instruction and achievement: A meta-analysis of the causal evidence". *Review of Educational Research*, 88(4), 547-588.
- Leary, M. R. (2018). "Toward a conceptualization of interpersonal rejection". *The Oxford handbook of social exclusion*.
- Leko, M. M., & Handy, T. (2019). Literacy Instruction for Adolescents with Learning Disabilities: Examining Teacher Practice and Preparation. *Learning Disabilities: A Contemporary Journal*, 17(1), 117-138. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1218036.pdf>
- Llego, M. A. (2019). 2019 DepEd Teacher Induction Program (TIP) TeacherPH. Retrieved from <https://www.teacherph.com/teacher-induction-program/Methods Approaches>. 4th Edition, SAGE Publications, Inc., London.
- Llego, M. A. (2022, August 25). Inclusive Education in the Philippines. TeacherPH. Retrieved August 25, 2022 from, <https://www.teacherph.com/inclusiveeducation-philippines/>
- Locke and Latham (2019). Building a practically useful theory of goal setting and task motivation: A 35-year odyssey. *American Psychologist*, 57(9), 705-717.
- Magnusson, G. 2019. "An Amalgam of Ideals – Images of Inclusion in the Salamanca Statement." *International Journal of Inclusive Education* 23 (7–8): 677–690. doi:10.1080/13603116.2019.1622805.
- Masten, A. S. (2019). "Global perspectives on resilience in children and youth". *Child Development*, 85(1), 6-20.
- Mastropieri, M. A., & Scruggs, T. E. (2018). The What, Why, and How of Evidence-Based Practice in Special Education. *Learning Disability Quarterly*, 41(1), 7–14. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0731948717744669>
- Maree, K., & Westhuizen, C. V. D. (2007). Preparation for research: The selection of research methodology. Van Schaik Publishers (pp. 13-27).
- Meiklejohn, J., Phillips, C., Freedman, M. L., Griffin, M. L., Biegel, G., Roach, A., ... & Saltzman, A. (2020). Integrating mindfulness training into K-12 education: Fostering the resilience of teachers and students. *Mindfulness*, 3(4), 291-307.
- Merriënboer, J. J. G. van, & Paas, F. (2019). "PowerPoint-based multimedia in learning: Why and why not?". *Educational Technology, Research and Development*, 51(2), 55-67.
- Meyer, A., Rose, D. H., & Gordon, D. (2014). *Universal design for learning: Theory and practice*. CAST Professional Publishing.
- Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Qualitative data analysis: An expanded sourcebook*. Sage Publications.
- McLeskey, J., Rosenberg, M. S., & Westling, D. L. (2021). *Inclusion: Effective practices for all students* (2nd ed.). Pearson.
- Morrow, S. L. (2005). Quality and trustworthiness in qualitative research in counseling psychology. *Journal of counseling psychology*, 52(2), 250
- Munhall, 2015; Scott, (2013). What Makes Qualitative Research Good Research? An Exploratory Analysis of Critical Elements: *International Journal of SocialScience Research* 5(5 2) <http://dx.doi.org/10.5296/ijssr.v5i2.10711..>
- Ní Bhroin, Ó., & King, F. (2020). Teacher education for inclusive education: a framework for developing collaboration for the inclusion of students with support plans. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(1), 38-63. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2019.1691993>
- Nunez, R., & Rosales, S. (2021). Inclusive Education: Perceptions and attitudes among Filipino high school teachers. *The Asian ESP*, 17(6.1), 151-172.

- Quejada, A. B., & Orale, R. L. (2018). Lived Experiences of Elementary Teachers in a Remote School in Samar, Philippines. *Journal of Academic Research*, 3(3), 1-13.
- Reeve, J. (2018). "Understanding motivation and emotion" (7th ed.). Hoboken, NJ: Wiley.
- Republic of the Philippines. (2012). Republic Act No. 10173: Data Privacy Act of 2012. Retrieved from <https://www.privacy.gov.ph/>
- Ronfeldt, M., & Grossman, P. (2021). "The Role of Mentoring in Novice Teacher Development: A Longitudinal Study." *Journal of Teacher Education*.
- Shenton, A. K. (2004). Strategies for ensuring trustworthiness in qualitative research projects. *Education for Information*, 22(2), 63-75. <https://doi.org/10.3233/EFI-2004-22201>
- Skrtic, T. M., & Elhower, S. E. (2004). The self-efficacy of teachers in inclusive education settings. *Journal of Special Education*, 37(4), 222-230.
- Smith A., Flower P. and Larkin M., (2009), *Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis: Theory, Method and Research*, 6(4), pp. 346–347
- Smith, A., Jones, B., & Johnson, C. (2019). Novice teachers' experiences in inclusive education: Challenges, supports, and professional development needs. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 87, 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2019.102936>
- Smith, A., & Tyler, D. (2020). Inclusive Education: A Systems Approach to Quality and Equity. *Journal of Inclusive Education*, 24(3), 218-232.
- Sweller, J., (2018). Cognitive load during problem solving: Effects on learning, *Cognitive Science*, 12, 257-285.
- Stahl, N., & King, J. (2020). Expanding approaches for research: Understanding and using trustworthiness in qualitative research. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346425936_Expanding_Approaches_for_Research_Understanding_and_Using_Trustworthiness_in_Qualitative_Research
- Subarna, M., Masud, N., Mensah, J., San, S., Hasan, M. and Tania, J. (2022) Teaching Strategies for Students with Disabilities in Regular Classes. *Creative Education*, 13, 1843-1861. doi: 10.4236/ce.2022.136116.
- Sutton, J. and Austin, Z. (2015) *Qualitative Research: Data Collection, Analysis, and Management*. *The Canadian Journal of Hospital Pharmacy*, 68, 226-231. <https://doi.org/10.4212/cjhp.v68i3.1456>
- Thorne, S., (2000). Data analysis in Qualitative Research: *Research Gate* <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/ebn.3.3.68>
- Toquero, C. M. D. (2020). Inclusion of people with disabilities amid COVID-19: Laws, interventions, recommendations. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Educational Research*, 10(2), 158-177. <https://doi.org/10.17583/remie.2020.5877>
- Turner, D., Harris, A., Mitchell, L., & Thompson, J. (2019). The role of parental support in teaching students with special needs. *Journal of Special Education*, 63(2), 82-96.
- Woulfin, S. L., & Jones, B. (2021). Special development: The nature, content, and structure of special education teachers' professional learning opportunities. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 100, 103277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2021.103277>
- Vaughn, S. and Fletcher, J. (2018) "Response to Intervention: Preventing and Remediating Academic Difficulties," *Child Development Perspectives* 3, no. 1: 30–37;
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Young, K. D., Grainger, P., & James, D. (2018). Attracting pre-service teachers to an inclusive education. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(2), 157-163. <http://dx.doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2018v43n2.9>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Lady Anne A. Dayanan

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Rhea Joy B. Semblante, PhD

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines